

Limit Preservation and Adjoint Functors

Sergio F. Tapia
Independent Researcher
Sydney, Australia

Preface

This manuscript is an expository monograph developing the categorical machinery leading to adjoint functors and examining the relationship between limit preservation and adjointness, including the role of the solution set condition and Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem.

The aim is to present a self-contained treatment accessible to readers with background in basic algebra and topology, while emphasising the structural reasons adjoint functors arise naturally throughout mathematics.

Abstract

Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem is commonly viewed as providing sufficient conditions for the existence of left adjoints via limit preservation together with the solution set condition. Equally significant, however, is the converse structural consequence: the existence of a left adjoint forces the preservation of limits.

This work develops the categorical machinery leading to adjoint functors and examines this implication in detail. Through a sequence of constructions and examples drawn from different areas of mathematics, we see that identifying a left adjoint leads to the discovery of non-trivial and interesting limits in categories.

The aim is to clarify the relationship between limit preservation and adjointness, and to gain a deeper appreciation of why adjoint functors arise throughout mathematics.

Acknowledgments

The author is grateful to Dr. Adam Harris for his invaluable guidance, support, and feedback throughout the preparation of this thesis, and to Dr. Imre Bokor for his early guidance and insightful discussions.

Contents

Preface	2
Abstract	3
1 Introduction	1
2 Categories	3
2.1 First definitions	3
2.2 Classes, sets and size	4
2.3 The category Set and concrete categories	4
2.3.1 Monoids as categories	4
2.3.2 The category of groups	5
2.3.3 The category of Abelian groups	5
2.3.4 The category of unital rings	6
2.4 Further examples of categories	7
2.4.1 Category of preorders	7
2.4.2 Categories from preorders	7
2.4.3 Discrete category	7
2.4.4 The opposite category	8
2.4.5 Vector spaces	8
2.4.6 Directed graphs	8
2.4.7 Product of categories	9
2.4.8 Category of complete metric spaces	10
2.4.9 Category of all small categories	10
3 Functors	11
3.1 Definition	11
3.2 Examples of functors	11
3.2.1 The covariant hom functor	11
3.2.2 The contravariant hom functor	12
3.2.3 Inclusion functor \mathcal{I}_D^C	13
3.2.4 The functor from Set to vector spaces	14
3.2.5 The functor from Set to groups	14
3.2.6 Covariant powerset functor	15
3.2.7 Abelianisation functor $F: \mathbf{Grp} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ab}$	16
3.2.8 Functors between monoids as categories	16
3.2.9 Forgetful functors	17
4 Natural Transformations	18
4.1 Definition	18
4.2 Vector spaces: V^* and V^{**}	18
4.3 Natural transformations induced by morphisms	20

4.4	The flattening operation	20
5	Fundamental Constructions	22
5.1	Products	22
5.1.1	Product of two objects	22
5.1.2	General definition of a product	23
5.1.3	Uniqueness of products	23
5.1.4	Coproducts	24
5.2	Equalisers and coequalisers	24
5.3	Pullbacks and pushouts	25
5.4	Special objects and morphisms	26
5.4.1	Monomorphisms and epimorphisms	26
5.4.2	Initial, terminal and zero objects	26
6	Limits	28
6.1	Cones and cocones	28
6.2	Defining a limit	29
6.3	Examples of limits	29
6.3.1	Products and coproducts as limits and colimits	29
6.3.2	Equalisers and coequalisers as limits and colimits.	30
6.3.3	Pullbacks and pushouts as limits	30
6.3.4	Limits and colimits as terminal and initial objects	31
6.4	Completeness	31
7	Adjoint Functors	33
7.1	Motivations	33
7.2	Hom-set perspective	33
7.3	Morphism only perspective	35
7.4	Unit and co-unit of adjunction	35
7.5	Universal morphism perspective	36
7.5.1	Left adjoint	37
7.5.2	Right adjoint	37
7.6	Combining Adjoint Definitions	37
8	The Freyd Adjoint Functor Theorem	40
8.1	Adjoints and limit preservation	40
8.2	A comma category	42
8.3	The theorem	44
8.4	Examples	46
8.4.1	$Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ and Set	46
8.4.2	Free Groups	46
8.4.3	Exponential law for sets	47
8.5	Further illustrative examples	48
8.5.1	Quantifiers	48
8.5.2	Propositional logic	49
8.5.3	Linear adjunction and subspaces of a normed linear space	51
8.5.4	Topological spaces	54
	References	57

Chapter 1

Introduction

In its original form, the concept of adjunction may be traced to the theory of linear spaces, where the passage from a Vector space V to its dual V^* entails the adjunction of linear maps, i.e., $f : V \rightarrow W$ induces $f^* : W^* \rightarrow V^*$, where

$$f^*(\varphi) = \varphi \circ f$$

for every linear functional $\varphi \in W^*$. This may be formulated in the language of categories and morphisms as saying that there is a contravariant functor

$$* : Vec_{\mathbb{F}} \rightarrow Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$$

which induces a natural isomorphism

$$Hom(V, W) \cong Hom(W^*, V^*).$$

We can examine the nature of this isomorphism, without the arbitrary choice of an inner product, if we consider instead morphisms $f \in Hom(V, W^*)$ and then define $f^* : W \rightarrow V^*$ such that for all $v \in V$, $w \in W$,

$$f^*(w)(v) = f(v)(w).$$

Given the canonical isomorphism $(V^*)^* \cong V$, it follows at once that $f^{**} = f$, hence

$$Hom(V, W^*) \cong Hom(W, V^*).$$

This leads to the following generalization: given a functor $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$, then $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ is the left adjoint of G if for all objects C in \mathcal{C} and D in \mathcal{D} we have a natural bijection between the sets of morphisms $C(G(D), C)$ and $D(D, F(C))$. It follows that $* : Vec_{\mathbb{F}} \rightarrow Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ is a self-adjoint functor. But what criteria determine the existence of a left adjoint for functors more generally? The answer to this is the Adjoint Functor Theorem, proven by Peter Freyd in 1964.

First, to appreciate the breadth of the question, consider the real number line \mathbb{R} as a category, in which the objects are the real numbers themselves, and morphisms are supplied by the natural order relation. In particular, because the real number line is totally ordered, we can say that the set $\mathbb{R}(a, b)$ consists of a unique morphism precisely when $a \leq b$, and is empty otherwise. A covariant functor $G : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is therefore a non-decreasing function, i.e., $a \leq b$ implies $G(a) \leq G(b)$, for which a left adjoint F must satisfy

$$x \leq F(y) \iff G(x) \leq y.$$

A natural choice for F would therefore be

$$F(y) = \sup\{x | G(x) \leq y\},$$

noting that $F(y)$ is uniquely defined if the range $R(G)$ has no upper bound. Moreover, this definition, together with the monotonicity of G , requires that $G(F(y)) = y$ whenever $y \in R(G)$. This condition is met if G is left semi-continuous, i.e., for all $a \in R$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow a^-} G(x) = G(a)$. It then follows that F is a right semi-continuous, non-decreasing function.

Returning to the more general categorical definition of left adjunction, we note that the sets of morphisms within \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{C} can at best be expected to provide a partial ordering among their objects, nonetheless existence of some form of “maximal” element, or collection of maximal elements, within the set of all morphisms in the image of G which target a given object C of \mathcal{C} , is evidently crucial to the definition of a left adjoint F . Similarly, a condition which guarantees that G “preserves limits” in an appropriately directed sense is also needed. It is one of the remarkable features of Category Theory, broadly conceived, that general conditions of this kind can be made both precise and meaningful across a wide range of very different categories.

Although the reader is assumed to have a nodding acquaintance with the most elementary notions, a formal introduction to categories and the basic properties of functors is covered systematically in chapters one to five of this monograph. There the reader will find a thorough discussion of natural transformations and the universal constructions, such as products, pull-backs and cones, which are essential to a precise definition of limits in chapter six. This concept, and the categorical definition of completeness that accompanies it, is in many ways the heart of the entire development. Like the concept of adjunction, limits reflect their initial formulation in the theory of metric spaces, but turn out to be ubiquitous, occurring in different guises throughout mathematics. Adjunction of functors is then discussed from a variety of standpoints in chapter seven. Here and in chapter eight, where the Adjoint Functor Theorem of Freyd is finally stated and proven, examples and specific illustrations of the general ideas are crucial to the discussion, and a rich array of categories in which this theorem is realized is examined in detail, especially in sections 8.4 and 8.5. One can find no more striking instance of its reach than the example of the small category of objects defined by the power set of a given set, and morphisms defined by the partial ordering induced by subset-inclusion. A function between two sets then induces a functor between their power sets, and it was the search for a left and right adjoint to functors of this type that led Lawvere to his remarkable discovery of the role played by the existential and universal quantifiers (cf. section 8.5.1).

We have alluded already to the functorial preservation of limits as being part of a sufficient condition for existence of left adjoints as formalized in Freyd’s Theorem, but as the numerous explicit cases of adjunction indicate, it is an equally important consequence of the theorem that existence of a left adjoint conversely implies preservation of limits. This fact has its practical uses, but if a single reason for the utility of Freyd’s Theorem were required it would perhaps be this: through the study of adjunction in propositional logic which followed on Lawvere’s work, the Adjoint Functor Theorem became an organizing principle for the application of Category Theory to the grammatical and semantic structure of natural languages, and more recently to the constantly changing architecture of computer programming languages and in examining Large Language Models. A satisfactory exploration of these exciting and very active areas of contemporary research is, however, beyond the scope of this monograph.

Chapter 2

Categories

In this chapter, we begin with the fundamentals of category theory through defining a category, considering set theoretic conditions and finally presenting various examples. It is hoped that through the examples of this chapter, the abstract definition of a category is appreciated, as it will subsume ideas and concepts from different fields in mathematics into a single universal language, giving insights into those fields and even between. When discussing the language of **Set**, objects will be sets themselves, while morphisms will be functions. When discussing complete metric spaces, objects will become complete metric spaces, while morphisms will assume the structure of continuous functions. Categories derived from pre-ordered sets will show the flexibility of category theory, when we understand that a morphism can be unrelated to a function as we may be familiar with, but can be something more abstract, such as an order relation between sets. In reading this chapter, objects of categories may begin to take center stage in your attention, but keep in mind that the morphisms are just as important, if not more so. Very quickly, from chapter three, we will begin to realise the importance of morphisms in category theory.

2.1 First definitions

Definition 2.1.1. A category \mathcal{C} consists of:

1. A class of objects, denoted $ob(\mathcal{C})$, and
2. A class of morphisms, $mor(\mathcal{C})$, whereby between any two objects A, B in \mathcal{C} , $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ represents the set (possibly empty) of morphisms from A to B , also known as a homset. For any morphism $f : A \rightarrow B$ in $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$, f has domain A , denoted by $dom(f)$, and codomain B , denoted $codom(f)$.

the objects and morphisms must satisfy the following:

- i. For any objects A, B, C in \mathcal{C} and morphisms $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $g : B \rightarrow C$, there is a given morphism $g \circ f : A \rightarrow C$; the composition of f and g .
- ii. For any f in $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$, g in $\mathcal{C}(B, C)$ and h in $\mathcal{C}(C, D)$,

$$h \circ (g \circ f) = (h \circ g) \circ f;$$

- iii. $\mathcal{C}(A, B) \cap \mathcal{C}(C, D) = \emptyset$ unless $A = C$ and $B = D$
- iv. For every object A in \mathcal{C} there is a given morphism 1_A in $\mathcal{C}(A, A)$; the identity morphism on A .

v. For any f in $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ and g in $\mathcal{C}(B, C)$;

$$\begin{aligned} f &= 1_B \circ f \quad \text{and} \\ g &= g \circ 1_B \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.1.2. A *small* category \mathcal{C} is one in which $ob(\mathcal{C})$ and $mor(\mathcal{C})$ are sets. Category \mathcal{C} is *locally small* if each $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ is a set.

Axiom 1 of definition 2.1.1 introduces the term *class* of objects and definition 2.1.2 refers to a category's size, these ideas are now explained.

2.2 Classes, sets and size

A category can be defined in various ways, which is dependent upon the foundation used. The preceding section has defined a category on the basis of the set theory of von Neumann-Gödel-Bernays. Briefly, a set is fixed as a universe \mathcal{U} , where the elements of \mathcal{U} are themselves sets. A class can be a set or larger than a set; a subset of elements of \mathcal{U} , known as a proper class. To put this into context, definition 2.1.1 discusses $mor(\mathcal{C})$ as a class of morphisms, and $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ as a set of morphisms, then we can define;

$$mor(\mathcal{C}) = \bigcup_{A, B \text{ in } ob(\mathcal{C})} \mathcal{C}(A, B)$$

For greater detail on the von Neumann-Gödel-Bernays basis for category theory consult [22], for a survey of set theoretic foundations of category theory see [23]. In [14], Mac Lane discusses the limitations that set theory imposes on a complete theory of categories, while in the appendix of [15], he defines categories without set theory, suggesting that categories without a set theory basis could potentially be a foundation for all mathematics.

2.3 The category **Set** and concrete categories

The category **Set**, which is locally small, contains sets as its objects and functions between sets as the morphisms between objects. Composition and associativity of morphisms of **Set** is satisfied by function composition and the associativity of functions. Identity morphisms in **Set** are simply identity functions of sets.

Categories in which the objects are sets with additional structure are termed **concrete categories**, some of these are defined in the following sections.

2.3.1 Monoids as categories

A monoid $(S, *)$ consists of a set S and a binary operation $*$ on S ,

$$* : S \times S \rightarrow S, \quad (x, y) \mapsto x * y$$

such that the following axioms are satisfied:

(1) Associativity. For all $x, y, z \in S$

$$(x * y) * z = x * (y * z)$$

(2) Identity element. There exists an identity element $1 \in S$ where for all $x \in S$,

$$x * 1 = 1 * x = x$$

Between any two monoids $(M, *)$ and (N, \bullet) we have a homomorphism,

$$\phi : (M, *) \rightarrow (N, \bullet).$$

such that

$$\phi(m * m') = \phi(m) \bullet \phi(m') \text{ and } \phi(1_M) = 1_N$$

for all $m, m' \in M$.

The category of monoids, known as **Mon**, consists of; all monoids as its objects, homomorphisms as the morphisms between monoids. Another important and interesting result with respect to monoids can be stated as;

Every monoid is a small category with a single object

here the set of morphisms of the category are the elements of the underlying set, subject to the binary operator of the monoid. That is, consider a monoid (M, \bullet) as a category with a single object, call that object $*$. For notational convenience call this category \mathcal{M} . Then $\text{ob}(\mathcal{M}) = \{*\}$ and $\mathcal{M}(*, *) = M$. Here the identity morphism of the category is the identity element of M and composition of morphisms is given by the monoid binary operator \bullet . As a concrete example, consider the monoid of positive integers (\mathbb{Z}^+, \times) with object $*$. Call this category \mathcal{Z} , where $\text{ob}(\mathcal{Z}) = \{*\}$ and $\mathcal{Z}(*, *) = \mathbb{Z}^+$. For any $x, y, z \in \mathcal{Z}(*, *) = \mathbb{Z}^+$,

$$\begin{aligned} (x \times y) \times z &= x \times (y \times z) \\ 1 \times x &= x \times 1 = x \end{aligned}$$

Here the positive integer 1 is the identity morphism.

2.3.2 The category of groups

A Group $(G, *)$ consists of a set G and a binary operation $*$ on G ,

$$* : G \times G \rightarrow G, \quad (g, g') \mapsto g * g'$$

A group is subject to the associativity and identity element of the monoid, axioms (1) and (2). There is a third axiom that the group is subject to, which the monoid is not, that is the existence of inverse elements in G . That is, for every $g \in G$ there exists an element $\bar{g} \in G$ such that,

$$g * \bar{g} = \bar{g} * g = 1$$

where 1 is the identity element. Similarly to monoids, the functions between groups are homomorphisms where, for $\phi : G \rightarrow H$,

$$\phi(g * g') = \phi(g) \bullet \phi(g') \text{ and } \phi(1_G) = 1_H$$

here $g, g' \in G$ and G, H are any groups.

The category **Grp** is the category with groups as objects and group homomorphisms as morphisms between objects.

2.3.3 The category of Abelian groups

Elements of an abelian group are subject to the group axioms; associativity, the existence of an identity element and the existence of an inverse element. Furthermore, the abelian group is also

subject to a fourth axiom of commutativity; for every element a, b in the abelian group $(A, *)$

$$a * b = b * a$$

The homomorphism ϕ from abelian groups $(A, *)$ to (A', \bullet) has an extra dimension due to its commutativity; for any $a, b \in A$

$$\phi(a * b) = \phi(a) \bullet \phi(b) = \phi(b) \bullet \phi(a) = \phi(b * a)$$

and as for groups,

$$\phi(1_A) = 1_{A'}$$

The category **Ab** is the category consisting of abelian groups as objects and abelian homomorphisms as the morphisms between objects. Composition of morphisms is governed by the abelian homomorphisms and the identity morphisms for any abelian group A in $ob(\mathbf{Ab})$ is 1_A in $\mathbf{Ab}(A, A)$.

Interesting relationships between **Grp** and **Ab** include;

1. **Ab** is a full subcategory of **Grp**. This is true since;
 - (a) Every abelian group in $ob(\mathbf{Ab})$ is in $ob(\mathbf{Grp})$, since an abelian group is a group.
 - (b) Every homomorphism of **Ab** is a homomorphism of **Grp**
 - (c) The identity morphism of an object A in **Ab**, 1_A in $\mathbf{Ab}(A, A)$, is the same identity morphism as that of object A in **Grp**, 1_A in $\mathbf{Grp}(A, A)$
 - (d) For any morphisms f, g in **Ab**, $f \circ g$ in **Ab** is equivalent to $f \circ g$ in **Grp**
 - (e) For any A, B in $ob(\mathbf{Ab})$, $\mathbf{Ab}(A, B) = \mathbf{Grp}(A, B)$. This is true since for any f in $\mathbf{Ab}(A, B)$, f is in $\mathbf{Grp}(A, B)$. Conversely, consider any f' in $\mathbf{Grp}(A, B)$, where A and B are subject to commutativity, then f' is in $\mathbf{Ab}(A, B)$.

Conditions (a)-(d) show that **Ab** is a subcategory of **Grp**, whilst (a)-(e) shows **Ab** to be a full subcategory of **Grp**.

2. A fascinating fact we find in [3] is that the groups in **Grp** are the abelian groups.

2.3.4 The category of unital rings

A unital ring $(S, +, \cdot)$ consists of a set S and binary operators $+$ and \cdot

$$\begin{aligned} + : S \times S &\rightarrow S, (x, y) \mapsto x + y && \text{(addition)} \\ \cdot : S \times S &\rightarrow S, (x, y) \mapsto x \cdot y && \text{(multiplication)} \end{aligned}$$

where we denote $x \cdot y$ as xy such that:

- (1) S is a monoid with respect to multiplication,
- (2) S is an abelian group with respect to addition,
- (3) for all $x, y, z \in S$

$$\begin{aligned} x(y + z) &= xy + xz && \text{and} \\ (x + y)z &= xz + yz \end{aligned}$$

Given conditions (1) and (2), a homomorphism between two unital rings, $(R, +, \cdot)$ to $(R', +, \cdot)$, is a mapping such that,

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(x +_R y) &= \psi(x) +_{R'} \psi(y), \\ \psi(x \cdot_R y) &= \psi(x) \cdot_{R'} \psi(y) \quad \text{and} \\ \psi(1_R) &= 1_{R'}\end{aligned}$$

where $x, y \in R$ and 1 is the multiplicative neutral element.

The category of unital rings consists of unital rings as objects and ring homomorphisms as the morphisms between objects. Composition of morphisms is governed by the underlying abelian group homomorphisms and the identity morphism for any unital ring object R is $1_R : R \rightarrow R, x \mapsto x$.

2.4 Further examples of categories

2.4.1 Category of preorders

Let S be a set and $x, y, z \in S$. A preorder is a set with a binary relation, call it (S, \preceq_S) , where the relation is:

$$\begin{aligned}x \preceq_S x &\quad (\text{Reflexive}) \\ x \preceq_S y \text{ and } y \preceq_S z &\text{ then } x \preceq_S z \quad (\text{Transitive})\end{aligned}$$

A category of preorders, \mathcal{P} , can be constructed by letting the class of objects contain all preordered sets and the morphisms of \mathcal{P} to be monotonic functions $f \in \mathcal{P}((S, \preceq_S), (T, \preceq_T))$. Here, f is monotonically increasing if for any $x, y \in (S, \preceq_S)$,

$$f(x) \preceq_T f(y) \text{ whenever } x \preceq_S y$$

In category \mathcal{P} , composition and associativity of morphisms follows from the composition and associativity of monotonic functions and the identity morphism is $1_{(S, \preceq_S)} \in \mathcal{P}((S, \preceq_S), (S, \preceq_S))$. The identity morphisms are related to the reflexivity of the preordered sets,

$$1_{(S, \preceq_S)}(x) \preceq_S 1_{(S, \preceq_S)}(x) = x \preceq_S x.$$

2.4.2 Categories from preorders

We can construct categories from a preordered set, (S, \preceq_S) , as follows. Let each element of the set be an object and for any $x, y \in S$ let there be a single morphism from x to y if and only if $x \preceq y$. Reflexivity ensures the existence of identity morphisms and the transitive relation ensures morphisms can be composed.

2.4.3 Discrete category

A category is discrete if and only if the morphisms of the category are identity morphisms. As an example, consider any set C and construct the category \mathcal{C} such that each element in C is an object of \mathcal{C} , that is $\text{ob}(\mathcal{C})=C$. The morphisms of \mathcal{C} can be chosen to be a map from any element in $\text{ob}(\mathcal{C})$ to itself. This leads to the set of morphisms,

$$\mathcal{C}(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1_x : x \rightarrow x, & \text{if } x = y \\ \emptyset, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $x, y \in ob(\mathcal{C})$. Composition of morphisms, $g \circ f$, exists if and only if $g = 1_x$ and $f = 1_x$ for any $x \in ob(\mathcal{C})$.

2.4.4 The opposite category

Consider any category \mathcal{C} with any objects $A, B \in ob(\mathcal{C})$ and any $f \in \mathcal{C}(A, B)$. The opposite category, \mathcal{C}^{op} , contains the same objects as category \mathcal{C} , while the morphisms in \mathcal{C}^{op} have the directions of the arrows reversed. That is, for any $f \in \mathcal{C}(A, B)$ there is an $f^{op} \in \mathcal{C}^{op}(B, A)$. Composition of morphisms of \mathcal{C}^{op} is as for \mathcal{C} , but with the arrows reversed. Then, for any $f \in \mathcal{C}(A, B)$ and $g \in \mathcal{C}(B, C)$

$$g \circ f : A \rightarrow C$$

while for $f^{op} \in \mathcal{C}^{op}(B, A)$ and $g^{op} \in \mathcal{C}^{op}(C, B)$,

$$f^{op} \circ g^{op} : C \rightarrow A$$

Hence,

$$(g \circ f)^{op} = f^{op} \circ g^{op}$$

With respect to the identity morphisms, it is clear that any identity morphism on an object in \mathcal{C} is exactly the identity morphism on the same object in \mathcal{C}^{op} , since for any $A \in ob(\mathcal{C})$, reversing the arrows of $1_A : A \rightarrow A$ gives the same morphism.

The opposite category is our first instance, in this thesis, of the duality of category theory. As we progress further we will find more examples of duality, and although this thesis will not delve too deeply into this important and far reaching concept, it is important to realise that duality does not stop at arrow reversal. Oversimplifying the duality principle discussed in [15, Section II.1], if we can prove a theorem for a category, then the theorem for the opposite category is also true.

2.4.5 Vector spaces

The category of vector spaces over a field \mathbb{F} , commonly denoted as $\mathbb{F}\text{-Vect}$ or $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$, consists of vector spaces as objects and \mathbb{F} -linear transformations, linear mappings over \mathbb{F} , as morphisms between objects. Composition and associativity of morphisms follows from composition and associativity of the \mathbb{F} -linear transformations while the identity morphisms in $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ are the identity transformations over \mathbb{F} .

2.4.6 Directed graphs

A graph consists of a set of vertices V and a set of edges E . For a directed graph define the following functions

$$src : E \rightarrow V \quad (\text{Source})$$

$$tgt : E \rightarrow V \quad (\text{Target})$$

then, for $e \in E$ and $v_0, v_1 \in V$, the description of the following simple graph,

$$v_0 \xrightarrow{e} v_1$$

becomes

$$src(e) = v_0$$

$$tgt(e) = v_1.$$

From any directed graph \mathbf{G} we can construct a category generated by the graph, call it $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})$. Let the vertices of \mathbf{G} be the objects of $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})$. Hence, this will be a small category since the class of objects is the set of vertices, that is $ob(\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})) = V$. The morphisms between objects will be finite sequences of edges, $e_0 \dots e_n$, between a source vertex and a target vertex, which can be intuitively recognised as a path from one vertex to another. For clarity, consider $f \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})(v_0, v_n)$ in the following diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} v_0 & \xrightarrow{e_0} & v_1 & \xrightarrow{e_1} & \dots & \xrightarrow{e_n} & v_n \\ & & & & & & \\ v_0 & \xrightarrow{\quad f \quad} & & & & & v_n \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} dom(f) &= dom(e_0 \dots e_n) = src(e_0) = v_0 \\ codom(f) &= codom(e_0 \dots e_n) = tgt(e_n) = v_n \end{aligned}$$

Composition of morphisms is defined as the concatenations of edges,

$$f \circ g = e_0 \dots e_n \circ \hat{e}_0 \dots \hat{e}_m = e_0 \dots e_n \hat{e}_0 \dots \hat{e}_m$$

and concatenations of edges is associative, hence morphisms in $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})$ are associative. For any vertex v there is an identity morphism $1_v \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{G})(v, v)$.

2.4.7 Product of categories

Consider the categories \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} . Define the product of categories, $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}$, such that $ob(\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D})$ consists of all pairs (C, D) where $C \in \mathcal{C}$ and $D \in \mathcal{D}$. For any $f \in \mathcal{C}(C, C')$ and $g \in \mathcal{D}(D, D')$ let (f, g) be a morphism in $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}((C, D), (C', D'))$, that is

$$(f, g) : (C, D) \rightarrow (C', D')$$

where

$$f : C \rightarrow C' \text{ and } g : D \rightarrow D'$$

From this we see that

$$\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}((C, D), (C', D')) = \mathcal{C}(C, C') \times \mathcal{D}(D, D')$$

For any two morphisms $(d, e), (f, g)$ of $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}$, composition is applied component-wise,

$$(d, e) \circ (f, g) = (d \circ f, e \circ g)$$

For any three morphisms $(b, c), (d, e), (f, g)$ of $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}$, compositions are associative,

$$\begin{aligned} (b, c) \circ ((d, e) \circ (f, g)) &= (b, c) \circ (d \circ f, e \circ g) \\ (b \circ d \circ f, c \circ e \circ g) &= (b \circ d, c \circ e) \circ (f, g) \\ &= ((b, c) \circ (d, e)) \circ (f, g) \end{aligned}$$

For any $(C, D) \in ob(\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D})$, the identity morphism is

$$1_{(C, D)} \in \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}((C, D), (C, D)) = \mathcal{C}(C, C) \times \mathcal{D}(D, D)$$

then

$$1_{(C, D)} = (1_C, 1_D)$$

The above definitions show that the product of two categories is itself a category. A product of n categories, for $n > 2$, can also be shown to be a category.

2.4.8 Category of complete metric spaces

Recalling from topology that a complete metric space M is one in which every Cauchy sequence in M converges to a limit in M . For this category, the objects are complete metric spaces and the morphisms are continuous functions between them. Composition is as one would expect for functions and the identity morphism is a continuous function from a complete metric space to itself, where each element of the underlying set is mapped to itself.

2.4.9 Category of all small categories

As we shall see in the next chapter, chapter 3, there exists a special type of mapping, a functor, that enables us to map one category to another. If we consider a functor to be a morphism between categories, and small categories to be objects, then we can construct a category of small categories. Call this category \mathbf{Cat} and let $ob(\mathbf{Cat})$ be the collection of all small categories. This class of objects is larger than a set and hence avoids contradictions identified in Russel's paradox. That is, $ob(\mathbf{Cat})$ is a class, which is larger than a set, that contains sets. For the morphisms of \mathbf{Cat} ,

$$\mathbf{Cat}(X, Y) = \{F \mid F \text{ is a functor, } F : X \rightarrow Y \text{ for any } X, Y \text{ in } ob(\mathbf{Cat})\}$$

Composition of morphisms is as defined for functors, implying associativity, and for any small category X in $ob(\mathbf{CAT})$ the identity morphism is the identity functor.

Chapter 3

Functors

Functors are of paramount importance in category theory as they enable the relationships between categories to be understood and appreciated. As we have seen in the previous chapter, the single abstract definition of a category can be seamlessly applied universally to any mathematical structure we have encountered. Functors will enable the application of this universal categorical language to occur between categories.

This chapter will commence with the definitions of covariant and contravariant functors, and then provide many examples to illustrate their universal applicability.

3.1 Definition

Between any two categories \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} a functor, $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$, is a rule that consists of two components; mappings between objects and mappings between morphisms of the categories. That is, for any X, Y in $ob(\mathcal{C})$ and any morphism f in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$, FX is in $ob(\mathcal{D})$ and Ff is in $\mathcal{D}(FX, FY)$ such that;

1. $F(1_X) = 1_{FX}$ for any X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$
2. $F(g \circ f) = Fg \circ Ff$ for any f in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and g in $\mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$.

The functor described by the above definition is known as a **covariant** functor. It preserves identity morphisms, the direction of the arrows and compositions. A **contravariant** functor reverses arrows. To illustrate this let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ be a **contravariant** functor then, for any X, Y in $ob(\mathcal{C})$ and any morphism f in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$, FX is in $ob(\mathcal{D})$ and Ff is in $\mathcal{D}(FY, FX)$ such that;

1. $F(1_X) = 1_{FX}$ for any X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$
2. $F(g \circ f) = Ff \circ Fg$ for any f in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and g in $\mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$

From points 1 and 2 of the above definitions we see that functors preserve commutative diagrams.

3.2 Examples of functors

3.2.1 The covariant hom functor

Every object A in a locally small category \mathcal{C} defines a Hom functor from \mathcal{C} to **Set**

$$\mathcal{C}(A, -) : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$$

and for any object X in \mathcal{C}

$$\mathcal{C}(A, -)X = \mathcal{C}(A, X)$$

that is, this functor assigns to the object X in \mathcal{C} the set of morphisms of \mathcal{C} from object A to X . And for any morphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ of \mathcal{C}

$$\mathcal{C}(A, -)f = \mathcal{C}(A, f) : \mathcal{C}(A, X) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, Y)$$

where for any $g \in \mathcal{C}(A, X)$, it can be seen from the commutative diagram below that $f \circ g : A \rightarrow Y$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \\ g \uparrow & \nearrow f \circ g & \\ A & & \end{array}$$

Hence,

$$\mathcal{C}(A, f) : \mathcal{C}(A, X) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, Y), g \mapsto f \circ g$$

Therefore for any $h \in \mathcal{C}(A, X)$,

$$\mathcal{C}(A, f)h = f \circ h \tag{3.1}$$

To show $\mathcal{C}(A, -)$ is in fact a functor we need to satisfy points 1 and 2 above.

1. For any $X \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{C})$, $\mathcal{C}(A, -)(1_X) = \mathcal{C}(A, 1_X) : \mathcal{C}(A, X) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, X)$ and for any $g \in \mathcal{C}(A, X)$,

$$\mathcal{C}(A, 1_X)g = 1_X \circ g = g \quad (\text{using 3.1})$$

hence,

$$\mathcal{C}(A, 1_X) = 1_{\mathcal{C}(A, X)} = 1_{\mathcal{C}(A, -)X}$$

2. For any $f \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and $g' \in \mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$, $g' \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ then

$$\mathcal{C}(A, -)(g' \circ f) = \mathcal{C}(A, g' \circ f) : \mathcal{C}(A, X) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, Z)$$

Now consider any $h \in \mathcal{C}(A, X)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(A, g' \circ f)h &= (g' \circ f) \circ h \\ &= g' \circ (f \circ h) \quad (\text{morphism associativity}) \\ &= \mathcal{C}(A, g')(f \circ h) \quad (\text{using 3.1}) \\ &= \mathcal{C}(A, g')\mathcal{C}(A, f)h \quad (\text{using 3.1}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\mathcal{C}(A, g' \circ f) = \mathcal{C}(A, g') \circ \mathcal{C}(A, f)$$

3.2.2 The contravariant hom functor

Similarly to the covariant hom functor, every object B in a locally small category \mathcal{C} defines a Hom functor from \mathcal{C} to **Set**

$$\mathcal{C}(-, B) : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$$

and for any object X in \mathcal{C}

$$\mathcal{C}(-, B)X = \mathcal{C}(X, B)$$

that is, this functor assigns to the object X in \mathcal{C} the set of morphisms of \mathcal{C} from object X to B . And for any morphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ of \mathcal{C}

$$\mathcal{C}(-, B)f = \mathcal{C}(f, B) : \mathcal{C}(Y, B) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, B)$$

Now consider any $g \in \mathcal{C}(Y, B)$ then $g \circ f : X \rightarrow B$ and

$$\mathcal{C}(f, B) : \mathcal{C}(Y, B) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, B), g \mapsto g \circ f$$

Hence for any h in $\mathcal{C}(Y, B)$,

$$\mathcal{C}(f, B)h = h \circ f. \quad (3.2)$$

Showing $\mathcal{C}(-, B)$ is a functor:

1. For any $X \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{C})$, $\mathcal{C}(-, B)(1_X) = \mathcal{C}(1_X, B) : \mathcal{C}(X, B) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, B)$ and for any $u \in \mathcal{C}(X, B)$,

$$\mathcal{C}(1_X, B)u = u \circ 1_X = u \quad (\text{using 3.2})$$

hence,

$$\mathcal{C}(1_X, B) = 1_{\mathcal{C}(X, B)} = 1_{\mathcal{C}(-, B)X}$$

2. For any $f \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and $g' \in \mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$, $g' \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ then

$$\mathcal{C}(-, B)(g' \circ f) = \mathcal{C}(g' \circ f, B) : \mathcal{C}(Z, B) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, B).$$

For any $h \in \mathcal{C}(Z, B)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(g' \circ f, B)h &= h \circ (g' \circ f) \\ &= (h \circ g') \circ f \quad (\text{morphism associativity}) \\ &= \mathcal{C}(f, B)(h \circ g') \\ &= \mathcal{C}(f, B)\mathcal{C}(g', B)h. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\mathcal{C}(g' \circ f, B) = \mathcal{C}(f, B) \circ \mathcal{C}(g', B).$$

3.2.3 Inclusion functor $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}$

In discussing the inclusion functor we need to first define a **subcategory**. The category \mathcal{D} is a subcategory of category \mathcal{C} if and only if

1. Every object of \mathcal{D} is an object of \mathcal{C} .
2. For all objects X, Y of \mathcal{D} , $\mathcal{D}(X, Y) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$
3. For any morphisms f, g of \mathcal{D} , $f \circ_{\mathcal{D}} g = f \circ_{\mathcal{C}} g$

Now let the category \mathcal{D} be a subcategory of the category \mathcal{C} and define the $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ such that,

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}X = X \text{ and } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}f = f$$

for any $X \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{C})$ and $f \in \mathcal{D}(X, Y)$. It is clear $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}f = f$, since $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}f \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}X, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}Y) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}X = X, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}Y = Y) = \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and by point 2 of the definition of a subcategory, $f \in \mathcal{D}(X, Y)$ is also $f \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$.

Showing that $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ is in fact a functor, consider any $X \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})$,

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}(1_X) = 1_X = 1_{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}X}$$

and for any $f \in \mathcal{D}(X, Y)$ and $g \in \mathcal{D}(Y, Z)$ then $g \circ f \in \mathcal{D}(X, Z)$, hence

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}(g \circ f) = g \circ f = \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}g \circ \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\mathcal{C}}f.$$

3.2.4 The functor from Set to vector spaces

Consider the rule $F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Vec}_{\mathbb{F}}$, where the set X is assigned to an \mathbb{F} vector space with basis X . Now define two components for this rule;

$$FX = \left\{ \sum_{x \in X} \lambda_x x \mid \lambda_x \in \mathbb{F} \text{ and } \lambda_x = 0 \text{ for all but finitely many } x \in X \right\},$$

$$Ff : FX \rightarrow FY, \sum_{x \in X} \lambda_x x \mapsto \sum_{x \in X} \lambda_x f(x)$$

where $f : X \rightarrow Y$. We state without proof that Ff is in fact an \mathbb{F} -linear transformation. Showing $F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Vec}_{\mathbb{F}}$ is a functor for any set X ,

$$F(1_X) : FX \rightarrow FX, \sum_{x \in X} \lambda_x x \mapsto \sum_{x \in X} \lambda_x x$$

hence,

$$F(1_X) = 1_{FX}.$$

Let $f : X \rightarrow Y, g : Y \rightarrow Z$ and $u = \sum_{x' \in X} \lambda_{x'} x' \in FX$ then,

$$\begin{aligned} (F(g \circ f))u &= \sum_{x' \in X} \lambda_{x'} (g \circ f)(x') \\ &= (Fg) \left(\sum_{x' \in X} \lambda_{x'} f(x') \right) \\ &= (Fg)(Ff(u)) \\ &= (Fg \circ Ff)u \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$F(g \circ f) = Fg \circ Ff.$$

3.2.5 The functor from Set to groups

For this example we will show that the rule $F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Grp}$, where a set X is assigned to the free¹ group on X , is a covariant functor. Define two components for this rule;

$$FX = \left\{ \prod_{x_i \in X} x_i^{e_i} \mid e_i \in \mathbb{Z}, i \geq 1 \right\},$$

$$Ff : FX \rightarrow FY, \prod_{x_i \in X} x_i^{e_i} \mapsto \prod_{x_i \in X} f(x_i)^{e_i}$$

where $f : X \rightarrow Y$. FX is the set of all reduced words, $\prod x_i^{e_i}$. Here a reduced word is a concatenation of elements of $x \in X$ where a word such as $x_1 x_2 x_2^{-1} x_3 = x_1 x_3$. FX can be shown to be a group with an identity element being the empty word. Note that reduced words cannot be commutative, e.g. $x_1 x_2 \neq x_2 x_1$, as not all groups have this abelian property. We call FX the free group on X . Ff is a group homomorphism between free groups FX and FY . Showing $F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Grp}$ is a functor for any set X ,

$$F(1_X) : FX \rightarrow FX$$

¹”free” relates to the unrestricted ability to construct the group from group axioms only, free from any other theories.

that is,

$$F(1_X) : \left\{ \prod_{x_i \in X} x_i^{e_i} \right\} \rightarrow \left\{ \prod_{x_i \in X} x_i^{e_i} \right\}$$

mapping the entire set FX to itself hence,

$$F(1_X) = 1_{FX}$$

When we let $f : X \rightarrow Y, g : Y \rightarrow Z$ and $u = \prod_{x_i \in X} x_i^{e_i} \in FX$ then

$$\begin{aligned} (F(g \circ f))u &= \prod_{x_i \in X} (g \circ f)(x_i^{e_i}) \\ &= (Fg) \left(\prod_{x_i \in X} f(x_i^{e_i}) \right) \\ &= (Fg)(Ff(u)) \\ &= (Fg \circ Ff)u \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$F(g \circ f) = Fg \circ Ff.$$

3.2.6 Covariant powerset functor

We are familiar with the powerset of a set X . If we consider sets as objects of **Set** then we can define the operation of the powerset as a covariant functor as follows. For any set X ,

$$\mathcal{P}(X) = \{U | U \subseteq X\}$$

and for any function f from sets A to B let,

$$\mathcal{P}f : \mathcal{P}X \rightarrow \mathcal{P}Y$$

where for any $U \in \mathcal{P}(X)$,

$$\mathcal{P}f(U) = f(U) = \{f(x) | x \in U\}. \quad (3.3)$$

Then $\mathcal{P} : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$. To prove that this is in fact a functor:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}1_X(U) &= \{1_X(x) | x \in U\} \\ &= \{x | x \in U\} \\ &= U \\ &= 1_{\mathcal{P}(X)}(U). \end{aligned}$$

For any functions $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(g \circ f)(U) &= \{(g \circ f)(x) | x \in U\} \\ &= \{g(f(x)) | x \in U\} \\ &= \{g(y) | y \in \{f(x) | x \in U\}\} \\ &= \mathcal{P}g(\{f(x) | x \in U\}) \\ &= \mathcal{P}g(\mathcal{P}f(U)) \\ &= (\mathcal{P}g \circ \mathcal{P}f)(U). \end{aligned}$$

3.2.7 Abelianisation functor $F : \mathbf{Grp} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ab}$

Let $G_{ab} = G/[G, G]$ where $[G, G]$ is the commutator, normal subgroup, of group G . G_{ab} is an abelian group, the abelianisation of G . For any homomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow H$, $\phi([G, G]) \subseteq [H, H]$ so ϕ induces a homomorphism $\phi_{ab} : G_{ab} \rightarrow H_{ab}$. To show that $F : \mathbf{Grp} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ab}$ is a functor define the following components,

$$\begin{aligned} FG &= G_{ab} \\ Ff &= f_{ab} \end{aligned}$$

where $f : G \rightarrow H$ is a group homomorphism. Here $Ff : FG \rightarrow FH = Ff : G_{ab} \rightarrow H_{ab} = f_{ab}$. Now for any group G ,

$$F(1_G) : FG \rightarrow FG$$

that is,

$$F(1_G) : G_{ab} \rightarrow G_{ab} = 1_{G_{ab}} = 1_{FG}$$

Finally, let $f : G \rightarrow H, g : H \rightarrow J$ then $g \circ f : G \rightarrow J$. Also consider any $z \in G_{ab} = G/[G, G] = \{z_i[G, G] \mid z_i \in G\} \subseteq G$, that is z is a coset in $G/[G, G]$ and so is in G . Now,

$$F(g \circ f) = (g \circ f)_{ab},$$

so at $z \in G_{ab}$

$$F(g \circ f)(z) = (g \circ f)_{ab}(z) = (g \circ f)(z).$$

Now consider,

$$Fg \circ Ff = g_{ab} \circ f_{ab}.$$

At $z \in G_{ab}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (g_{ab} \circ f_{ab})(z) &= g_{ab}(f_{ab}(z)) \\ &= g_{ab}(f(z)) \\ &= g(f(z)) \\ &= (g \circ f)(z). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$(Fg \circ Ff)(z) = (g_{ab} \circ f_{ab})(z) = (g \circ f)(z) = F(g \circ f)(z)$$

Therefore for any $z \in G_{ab}$,

$$Fg \circ Ff = F(g \circ f).$$

3.2.8 Functors between monoids as categories

When we consider a monoid as a category, as we did towards the end of section 2.3.1, we can see that a functor between two monoids is just a monoid homomorphism. To this end let (X, \oplus) and (Y, \bullet) be monoids and construct the categories \mathcal{M}_X and \mathcal{M}_Y each with a single object $*$ and \star , respectively. Specifically, let

$$\begin{aligned} ob(\mathcal{M}_X) &= \{*\}, \mathcal{M}_X(*, *) = X \\ ob(\mathcal{M}_Y) &= \{\star\}, \mathcal{M}_Y(\star, \star) = Y \end{aligned}$$

Define the functor $F : \mathcal{M}_X \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_Y$ with the component mappings;

$$\begin{aligned} F* &= \star \text{ in } \mathcal{M}_Y, \\ Ff : F* &\rightarrow F* \text{ in } \mathcal{M}_Y(\star, \star) = Y \end{aligned}$$

where $f \in \mathcal{M}_X(*, *) = X$. Now since F is a functor,

$$F(1_*) = 1_{F*}$$

for identity morphism $1_* \in \mathcal{M}_X(*, *)$. But $\mathcal{M}_X(*, *) = X$, then the identity morphism is simply the identity $e_X \in X$ hence

$$F(e_X) = F(1_*) = 1_{F*} = 1_* = e_Y$$

For any $f, g \in \mathcal{M}_X(*, *) = X$

$$F(g \oplus f) = Fg \oplus Ff = Fg \bullet Ff = F(g \bullet f)$$

since Fg and Ff are in (Y, \bullet) .

3.2.9 Forgetful functors

A forgetful functor will have a category, say \mathcal{C} , as its domain and a less structured version of the domain as its codomain. The objects and morphisms of the domain have their properties removed or forgotten. For example, the functor $F : \mathbf{Grp} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$ takes objects in \mathbf{Grp} and maps these to objects in the underlying sets. The group axioms and the binary operator, together with the homomorphic properties of the morphisms in \mathbf{Grp} have been forgotten by the codomain, \mathbf{Set} .

Chapter 4

Natural Transformations

In defining categories we have seen that between two objects of a category there can exist morphisms. Between any two functors we can also have a family of morphisms known as natural transformations. The natural transformation that the reader is likely most familiar with is within the category of vector spaces, considering the relationship between the dual and double dual of a vector space. It is in this example, presented below, that we can begin to grasp the necessity for a “natural transformation” in category theory. But first, this chapter will present the definition of natural transformations, for covariant and contravariant functors, followed by this foundational example and two more examples, including one related to computer programming, which hints at the universality of this concept.

4.1 Definition

Consider a pair of covariant functors $F, G : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$. We define a natural transformation $\eta : F \Rightarrow G$ as a family of morphisms in \mathcal{D} where for each X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$ there is a morphism, η_X in $\mathcal{D}(FX, GX)$, such that for any f in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ the following diagram commutes,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} FX & \xrightarrow{\eta_X} & GX \\ Ff \downarrow & & \downarrow Gf \\ FY & \xrightarrow{\eta_Y} & GY \end{array} \quad (4.1)$$

that is, $Gf \circ \eta_X = \eta_Y \circ Ff$. Here each η_X is a component of η . For contravariant functors $F, G : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ the natural transformation definition is much the same, except that Ff is in $\mathcal{D}(FY, FX)$ and Gf is in $\mathcal{D}(GY, GX)$, hence $Gf \circ \eta_Y = \eta_X \circ Ff$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} FX & \xrightarrow{\eta_X} & GX \\ Ff \uparrow & & \uparrow Gf \\ FY & \xrightarrow{\eta_Y} & GY \end{array} \quad (4.2)$$

We consider the following example to interpret this abstract definition with a familiar case, the relationship between vector spaces, their duals and double duals.

4.2 Vector spaces: V^* and V^{**}

From linear algebra we know that for a finite dimensional vector space V , there exists an isomorphism between V and V^* , but this isomorphism is dependent upon a choice of basis.

However, there exists a “natural” isomorphism between V and V^{**} , natural in the sense that the isomorphism will remain the same regardless of the choice of basis. To see this from a categorical perspective, define the following functors;

$$\begin{aligned} (-)^{**} : Vec_{\mathbb{F}} &\rightarrow Vec_{\mathbb{F}}, \\ V &\mapsto V^{**}, \\ (f : V \rightarrow W) &\mapsto (f^{**} : V^{**} \rightarrow W^{**}) \\ i : Vec_{\mathbb{F}} &\rightarrow Vec_{\mathbb{F}}, \\ V &\mapsto V, \\ (f : V \rightarrow W) &\mapsto (f : V \rightarrow W) \end{aligned}$$

where i is the identity functor. Now, for any vector space V in $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$, let us consider a transformation, η , from V to V^{**} , that is from $i(V)$ to $(-)^{**}(V)$. But, since we are dealing with mappings between functors then we must also consider mappings between morphisms f to f^{**} in $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$. If we now create a diagram connecting the objects together by their respective morphisms, starting at the top of the diagram with the mapping from V to V^{**} , then we naturally obtain the diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} V & \xrightarrow{\eta_V} & V^{**} \\ f \downarrow & & \downarrow f^{**} \\ W & \xrightarrow{\eta_W} & W^{**} \end{array} \quad (4.3)$$

But, we have already noticed that $i(V) = V$ and $(-)^{**}(V) = V^{**}$. Also, $i(f) = f$ and $(-)^{**}(f) = f^{**}$, then diagram 4.3 is equivalent to

$$\begin{array}{ccc} i(V) & \xrightarrow{\eta_V} & (-)^{**}(V) \\ i(f) \downarrow & & \downarrow (-)^{**}(f) \\ i(W) & \xrightarrow{\eta_W} & (-)^{**}(W) \end{array} \quad (4.4)$$

which, when compared to diagram 4.1, is precisely the definition of a natural transformation, we only need to check if the diagram commutes. Reconsidering diagram 4.3 and defining $\eta_V : V \rightarrow V^{**}, v \mapsto (eval_v : V^* \rightarrow \mathbb{F})$ where for any $g : V \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$ and $v \in V$, $eval_v(g) = g(v)$, $eval$ being the evaluation function of g at v . Then, for $h' : W \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (f^{**} \circ \eta_V)(v)(h') &= f^{**}(\eta_V)(v)(h') \\ &= f^{**}(eval_v)(h') \\ &= (eval_v \circ f^*)(h') \quad (\text{where } f^* : W^* \rightarrow V^*) \\ &= eval_v(f^*(h')) \\ &= eval_v(h' \circ f) \quad (\text{using } f^* \circ h' = h' \circ f, \text{ see equation 7.2}) \\ &= (h' \circ f)(v) \\ &= h'(f(v)) \\ &= eval_{f(v)}(h') \\ &= \eta_W(f(v))(h') \\ &= (\eta_W \circ f)(v)(h'). \end{aligned}$$

Hence the diagram commutes.

4.3 Natural transformations induced by morphisms

To see another example of a natural transformation, while highlighting the universality of the underlying theory, the following example has no relation to vector spaces, yet the underlying foundation of the natural transformation remains applicable to this vastly different case. Consider any category \mathcal{C} and let f be in $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ for any A, B in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, we can find a natural transformation, induced by f , between covariant functors $\mathcal{C}(B, -)$ and $\mathcal{C}(A, -)$, that is $\mathcal{C}(f, -) : \mathcal{C}(B, -) \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, -)$. To show this is a natural transformation consider any X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$,

$$\mathcal{C}(f, -)X = \mathcal{C}(f, X) : \mathcal{C}(B, X) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, X), \phi \mapsto \phi \circ f$$

Also for any g in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(B, g) : \mathcal{C}(B, X) &\rightarrow \mathcal{C}(B, Y), \\ \mathcal{C}(A, g) : \mathcal{C}(A, X) &\rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, Y). \end{aligned}$$

Since the compositions of morphisms in any category are commutative, then any morphism g in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ induces the following commutative diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{C}(B, X) & \xrightarrow{\mathcal{C}(f, X)} & \mathcal{C}(A, X) \\ \mathcal{C}(B, g) \downarrow & & \downarrow \mathcal{C}(A, g) \\ \mathcal{C}(B, Y) & \xrightarrow{\mathcal{C}(f, Y)} & \mathcal{C}(A, Y) \end{array}$$

Therefore,

$$\mathcal{C}(f, Y) \circ \mathcal{C}(B, g) = \mathcal{C}(A, g) \circ \mathcal{C}(f, X)$$

which becomes,

$$\mathcal{C}(f, -)Y \circ \mathcal{C}(B, g) = \mathcal{C}(A, g) \circ \mathcal{C}(f, -)X$$

hence $\mathcal{C}(f, -)$ is a natural transformation,

$$\mathcal{C}(f, -) : \mathcal{C}(B, -) \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}(A, -) \tag{4.5}$$

4.4 The flattening operation

For this example we consider a natural transformation that exists within the computer science domain, specifically programming. Here we show that the flattening operation is in fact a natural transformation. We can describe the flattening operation as an operation on a set of subsets, say $\{\{u, v, w\}, x, \{x, y\}, z\}$, which returns the set $\{u, v, w, x, y, z\}$. This operation is useful to a programmer when they have, for example, a list of lists and require a non-nested list. In mathematical terms we can describe the the flattening operation as a function from the powerset of the powerset of X to the powerset of X ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{flatten}_X : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(X)) &\rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X), \\ \mathcal{U} &\mapsto \bigcup_{U \in \mathcal{U}} U \end{aligned}$$

But, we have seen in section 3.2.6 that $\mathcal{P}(X)$ is in fact a covariant functor from **Set** to **Set**. Also, since $\mathcal{P}(X)$ is an object of **Set**, then the powerset of $\mathcal{P}(X)$ must also be a covariant functor from **Set** to **Set**. Hence, we can describe the flattening operation as a mapping between two

functors,

$$\text{flatten} : \mathcal{P} \circ \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}.$$

To show that flatten is a natural transformation, we will show that the following diagram commutes for any sets X, Y and function $f : X \rightarrow Y$:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} (\mathcal{P} \circ \mathcal{P})X & \xrightarrow{\text{flatten}_X} & \mathcal{P}X \\ (\mathcal{P} \circ \mathcal{P})f \downarrow & & \downarrow \mathcal{P}f \\ (\mathcal{P} \circ \mathcal{P})Y & \xrightarrow{\text{flatten}_Y} & \mathcal{P}Y \end{array}$$

To begin, for any $\mathcal{U} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(X))$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{P}f \circ \text{flatten}_X)(\mathcal{U}) &= (\mathcal{P}f)(\text{flatten}_X(\mathcal{U})) \\ &= (\mathcal{P}f)\left(\bigcup_{U \in \mathcal{U}} U\right) \\ &= \{f(U) \mid U \in \bigcup_{U \in \mathcal{U}} U\} \quad (\text{see equation 3.3}) \\ &= \{f(U) \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{flatten}_Y)((\mathcal{P} \circ \mathcal{P})f)(\mathcal{U}) &= (\text{flatten}_Y)((\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}f))(\mathcal{U})) \\ &= (\text{flatten}_Y)((\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}f)(\mathcal{U})) \\ &= (\text{flatten}_Y)(\mathcal{P}(\{f(U) \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\})) \\ &= \left\{ \bigcup_{V \in \mathcal{P}(\{f(U) \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\})} V \right\} \\ &= \{f(U) \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\} \quad (\text{since for any set } Z, Z = \bigcup_{z \in \mathcal{P}(Z)} z) \end{aligned}$$

Chapter 5

Fundamental Constructions

In this section we will define several fundamental objects that emerge throughout category theory, especially so in the chapters ahead. Section 5.1 introduces products, which is the archetypal example of the universal nature of category theory. Products and equalisers, the latter to be introduced in section 5.2, are necessary to prove the completeness theorem of section 6.4. As we shall see in section 5.3, through products and equalisers we can construct another fundamental structure, the pullback. To conclude this chapter, section 5.4 will introduce further special objects and morphisms. In discussing each fundamental construction, its dual construction, also fundamental, shall be discussed.

5.1 Products

We are familiar with the Cartesian product of two sets A and B , $A \times B = \{(a, b) \mid a \in A \text{ and } b \in B\}$. From a category theoretic perspective, for those categories that do have products, as not all do, we can extend this structure to a more general concept of a product of two objects, then we can generalise this further to a product of n objects.

5.1.1 Product of two objects

For a category \mathcal{C} and $A \times B$ in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, $(A \times B, f_A, f_B)$ is a product in \mathcal{C} if and only if,

- $f_A : A \times B \rightarrow A$, $f_B : A \times B \rightarrow B$ and
- for any X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, with morphisms $g_A : X \rightarrow A$ and $g_B : X \rightarrow B$, there exists a unique morphism $h \in \mathcal{C}(X, A \times B)$ such that $g_A = f_A \circ h$ and $g_B = f_B \circ h$,

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} & & X & & \\ & g_A \swarrow & & \searrow g_B & \\ A & \xleftarrow{f_A} & A \times B & \xrightarrow{f_B} & B \end{array}$$

$\exists! h$ (indicated by a dashed arrow from X to $A \times B$)

Emphasising the universality of the product; $(A \times B, f_A, f_B)$ is the most general construction of any object X of \mathcal{C} , which has morphisms to objects A and B and a unique map to $A \times B$, such that the above triangle commutes.

However, for some categories such as discrete categories with more than one object, they do not have products. To illustrate this, let us consider the example of a discrete category from section 2.4.3. In this example of a category, we have considered the elements of a set C as its objects and the only morphisms that exist are the identity morphisms between each object. Let us now consider any distinct objects $x_0, x_1, x_3 \in C$. When we attempt to construct a product

as described above we can go as far as the first point, constructing projections from $x_0 \times x_1$,

$$x_0 \xleftarrow{f_{x_0}} x_0 \times x_1 \xrightarrow{f_{x_1}} x_1$$

But we cannot go any further, since we cannot choose any object x_3 that has morphisms to x_0 and x_1 . Hence, the construction fails and the category cannot have products.

5.1.2 General definition of a product

Extending the discussion of a product of two objects to the general case.

Definition 5.1.1. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and I a set. For P in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, $(P, (f_i)_{i \in I})$ is a product in \mathcal{C} if and only if,

- for each $i \in I$, the morphism $f_i \in \mathcal{C}(P, A_i)$ and
- for any object X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, where for each $i \in I$ the morphism $g_i \in \mathcal{C}(X, A_i)$, there exists a unique morphism $h \in \mathcal{C}(X, P)$ such that $g_i = f_i \circ h$ for each i ,

5.1.3 Uniqueness of products

At this point we can define a product in a category and we are aware that some categories have products, some do not. But, are products within a category unique? The answer is that they are unique, up to isomorphism, and this is best understood from a proof of this statement.

Let $(P, (f_i)_{i \in I})$ and $(Q, (g_i)_{i \in I})$ both be products in the category \mathcal{C} . Also, for each i in an indexing set I , let $f_i \in \mathcal{C}(P, A_i)$ and let $g_i \in \mathcal{C}(Q, A_i)$. By the definition of a product, both P and Q are objects of category \mathcal{C} . Now let us focus on the product $(P, (f_i)_{i \in I})$ then there must be a unique morphism $h : Q \rightarrow P$, such that the following triangle commutes,

Then, $g_i = f_i \circ h$ for each i . Let us now focus on the product $(Q, (g_i)_{i \in I})$. There must be a unique morphism $h' : P \rightarrow Q$, such that the triangle commutes, that is, $f_i = g_i \circ h'$ for each i ,

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_i &= f_i \circ h \\
 &= (g_i \circ h') \circ h \\
 &= g_i \circ (h' \circ h) \\
 &= g_i \circ 1_Q.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} f_i &= g_i \circ h' \\ &= (f_i \circ h) \circ h' \\ &= f_i \circ (h \circ h') \\ &= f_i \circ 1_P. \end{aligned}$$

Then since $h' \circ h = 1_Q$ and $h \circ h' = 1_P$, h is an isomorphism and therefore the products are isomorphic.

5.1.4 Coproducts

While in the category **Set** a product is a cartesian product, it's dual, the coproduct, is a disjoint union of sets. And as with the case of products, not all categories will have a coproduct, certainly if a category does not have a product then it cannot have a coproduct, since they are dual to one another. But for any category with a coproduct, a coproduct is defined as follows.

Definition 5.1.2. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and I a set. For Q in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, $(Q, (f_i)_{i \in I})$ is a coproduct in \mathcal{C} if and only if,

- for each $i \in I$, the morphism $f_i \in \mathcal{C}(A_i, Q)$ and
- for any object X in $ob(\mathcal{C})$, where for each $i \in I$ the morphism $g_i \in \mathcal{C}(A_i, X)$, there exists a unique morphism $\hat{h} \in \mathcal{C}(Q, X)$ such that $g_i = \hat{h} \circ f_i$ for each i ,

5.2 Equalisers and coequalisers

For a category \mathcal{C} , consider any two morphisms f, g in $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$. Let the pair (Z, eq) represent an object Z in \mathcal{C} and a morphism eq in $\mathcal{C}(Z, X)$ such that $f \circ eq = g \circ eq$. Now consider any pair (W, w) where W is an object of \mathcal{C} and w is a morphism in $\mathcal{C}(W, X)$ such that $f \circ w = g \circ w$. The pair (Z, eq) is an **equaliser** of morphisms f, g if for any such pair (W, w) there exists a unique morphism h in $\mathcal{C}(W, Z)$ such that $w = eq \circ h$. Diagrammatically,

In the category **Set**, where $f, g : X \rightarrow Y$, the equaliser is simply the set $\{x \in X | f(x) = g(x)\}$. The dual of an equaliser, the **coequaliser**, is constructed by reversing the arrows of the triangle in the equaliser diagram above and shifting the focus from the domain of f, g to the codomain, as we can see from the diagram,

In this case, for any pair (W, w') such that $w' \circ f = w' \circ g$, the pair (Z, co) is a coequaliser of f, g if there exists and a unique morphism h' in $\mathcal{C}(Z, W)$ such that $w' = h' \circ co$.

5.3 Pullbacks and pushouts

Utilising products (coproducts) and equalisers (coequalisers) we can begin to construct pullbacks and their dual (pushouts). But as we saw previously, we cannot construct products and coproducts in every category, hence we cannot construct pullbacks and pushouts in every category. For categories that allow the construction of pullbacks and pushouts let us begin with there definitions.

Definition 5.3.1. Consider any category \mathcal{C} and a pair of morphisms f, g in $\mathcal{C}(A, C)$ and $\mathcal{C}(B, C)$ respectively. A **pullback** of f, g is given by a triple (P, f', g') where

- (1) P is an object of \mathcal{C} and
- (2) $f' \in \mathcal{C}(P, B)$ and $g' \in \mathcal{C}(P, A)$ where $f \circ g' = g \circ f'$

such that;

- (3) for any triple $(Q \text{ in } \text{ob}(\mathcal{C}), f'' \in \mathcal{C}(Q, B), g'' \in \mathcal{C}(Q, A))$ where $f \circ g'' = g \circ f''$, there exists a unique $h \in \mathcal{C}(Q, P)$ such that $f'' = f' \circ h$ and $g'' = g' \circ h$.

If the pullback diagram above was taken from the category **Set**, then the pullback would be the set $\{(a, b) \in A \times B | f(a) = g(b)\}$. The dual of the pullback, the pushout, is defined in a similar manner as the pullback but with all arrows reversed and commutativity maintained. The **pushout** of a pair of morphisms u, v is (P', u', v') , described diagrammatically as;

From the above definitions it is evident that 2-object, or binary, products are involved in the construction of pullbacks, binary coproducts for pushouts. In fact we can construct the pullback shown in definition 5.3.1 from a binary product and an equaliser. Referring to diagram 5.1, we see that the pullback can be constructed from a binary product $(P = A \times B, f', g')$ and an equaliser (Q, h) formed from the morphisms $g \circ f' : A \times B \rightarrow C$ and $f \circ g' : A \times B \rightarrow C$. Dually, referring to diagram 5.2, the pushout can be constructed from a coproduct $(P' = A' \amalg B', u', v')$ and a coequaliser (Q', \hat{h}) formed from $v' \circ u : C' \rightarrow A' \amalg B'$ and $u' \circ v : C' \rightarrow A' \amalg B'$.

5.4 Special objects and morphisms

5.4.1 Monomorphisms and epimorphisms

In the category **Set** we are familiar with injective and bijective functions. A monomorphism and epimorphism, respectively, is a generalisation of these familiar concepts to arbitrary categories. A morphism f in $\mathcal{C}(A, B)$ of a category \mathcal{C} is a **monomorphism** if for every object C in \mathcal{C} and morphisms g, h in $\mathcal{C}(C, A)$, $f \circ g = f \circ h \Rightarrow g = h$. Diagrammatically,

$$C \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{g} \\ \xrightarrow{h} \end{array} A \xrightarrow{f} B$$

A morphism f' in $\mathcal{C}(B, A)$ of a category \mathcal{C} is an **epimorphism** if for every object C in \mathcal{C} and morphisms g', h' in $\mathcal{C}(A, C)$, $g' \circ f' = h' \circ f' \Rightarrow g' = h'$. Diagrammatically,

$$C \begin{array}{c} \xleftarrow{g'} \\ \xleftarrow{h'} \end{array} A \xleftarrow{f'} B$$

It is clear from the definitions above that an epimorphism is the dual of a monomorphism. Equalisers and monomorphisms are related since,

every equaliser is a monomorphism.

To see this, refer to the diagram below, and suppose that (Z, eq) is an equaliser of morphisms f, g and let $h_1, h_2 : W \rightarrow Z$, such that $eq \circ h_1 = eq \circ h_2$. Note that $f \circ w = g \circ w$. Since (Z, eq) is an equaliser there exists a unique morphism h where $eq \circ h = w = eq \circ h_1 = eq \circ h_2$ then $h = h_1 = h_2$, therefore eq is a monomorphism.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} W & & & & \\ \downarrow h_2 & \searrow w & & & \\ \downarrow h & & & & \\ \downarrow h_1 & & & & \\ Z & \xrightarrow{eq} & X & \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} & Y \end{array}$$

Similarly,

every coequaliser is an epimorphism.

Suppose that (Z, co) is a coequaliser of morphisms f, g and let $h'_1, h'_2 : Z \rightarrow W$, such that $h'_1 \circ co = h'_2 \circ co$ and noting that $w' \circ f = w' \circ g$. Since (Z, co) is a coequaliser there exists a unique morphism h' where $h' \circ co = w' = h'_1 \circ co = h'_2 \circ co$ then $h' = h'_1 = h'_2$, therefore co is an epimorphism.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} & & & & W \\ & & & & \downarrow h'_2 \\ & & & & \downarrow h' \\ & & & & \downarrow h'_1 \\ X & \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} & Y & \xrightarrow{co} & Z \end{array}$$

5.4.2 Initial, terminal and zero objects

Consider any object A of a category \mathcal{C} . A is an **initial** object if and only if for every object X in \mathcal{C} , $\mathcal{C}(A, X)$ is a singleton set. A is a **terminal**, or **final**, object in \mathcal{C} if and only if for every object Y in \mathcal{C} , $\mathcal{C}(Y, A)$ is a singleton set. A is a **zero** object if and only if A is both an **initial** and **terminal** object. Examples of initial and terminal objects can be found in the category **Set**, which was introduced in section 2.3. In this category the empty set is the only

initial object and any singleton set is a terminal object, since for any set X we can map all of the elements of X to the element of a singleton set, this map being unique. In section 2.4.2, it was shown that we can construct a category from a preordered set. In this case, if there exists a least element in the preordered set, then the least element is an initial object in the category derived from the set. Dually, if there is a greatest element in the set, then this is the terminal object in the category. In the category **Grp**, see section 2.3.2, any trivial group, a group with an underlying singleton set, is both an initial and terminal object, hence it is a zero object. A trivial group is initial since a group with an underlying singleton set must have the identity element as the only member of that set. Then since homomorphisms map identity elements from one group to another, we can always define a unique homomorphism from a trivial group to any non-trivial group. A trivial group is also terminal since for any group we can map all of its elements to the identity element of the trivial group.

Chapter 6

Limits

We shall see in subsequent chapters that limits, and their preservation, play a central role in Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem. We will also discuss in various examples how the existence of a left adjoint functor implies limit preservation, which, in its own right, is interesting and important. This chapter will focus on developing the necessary categorical machinery to appreciate the role limits play in the later chapters of this monograph. The first two sections will develop the definition of a limit, this includes the concepts of diagrams, cones and cocones and universal cones and cocones. The examples presented in section 6.3 will tie together the concepts presented in sections 6.1 and 6.2 and will show that the foundational constructions; products, equalisers, pullbacks, terminal objects and their duals are all examples of limits and colimits. The final section will prove an important completeness theorem.

6.1 Cones and cocones

Before discussing limits we must first introduce the concept of a cone, which relies on the notions of a diagram and directed graphs, recall section 2.4.6 for a discussion on directed graphs. Consider a category \mathcal{D} and represent this as a directed graph, call it $\Sigma_{\mathcal{D}}$, with vertices being the objects and edges being the morphisms of \mathcal{D} . Then we can consider a *diagram* Σ_c in category \mathcal{C} as the image of a functor $F : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$. This functor enables the representation of the directed graph $\Sigma_{\mathcal{D}}$ as a directed graph in \mathcal{C} , Σ_c . A **cone** over a diagram Σ_c in \mathcal{C} , consists of an object C in \mathcal{C} and a family of morphisms for every object D in \mathcal{D} , $\{f_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})} \in \mathcal{C}(C, FD)\}$, such that for every morphism g in $\mathcal{D}(D, D')$, $f_{D'} = Fg \circ f_D$. This cone $(C, (f_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is illustrated by;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & C & \\ f_D \swarrow & & \searrow f_{D'} \\ FD & \xrightarrow{Fg} & FD' \end{array}$$

To give clarity to this categorical structure, which appears in many guises throughout mathematics, consider an example which is common and familiar from calculus, the limit of a sequence. To this end, consider a preordered set (\mathbb{R}, \leq) , such as was discussed in section 2.4.2, where the objects are the real numbers and for any $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ a single morphism exists from b to a if and only if $a \leq b$. For this example, consider a functor from (\mathbb{N}, \leq) to (\mathbb{R}, \leq) . A diagram in this category can be a monotone sequence of real numbers $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. A cone over this diagram will then be an upper bound of the sequence.

The dual of the cone is the **cocone**. A cocone under a diagram Σ_c in \mathcal{C} consists of an object C in \mathcal{C} and a family of morphisms for every object D in \mathcal{D} , $\{q_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})} \in \mathcal{C}(FD, C)\}$, such that for every morphism g in $\mathcal{D}(D', D)$, $q_{D'} = q_D \circ Fg$. The cocone $(C, (q_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is illustrated

by;

Using the example of (\mathbb{R}, \leq) above, the cocone will be the lower bound of the sequence.

6.2 Defining a limit

Definition 6.2.1. The limit, or universal cone, over a diagram Σ_c in \mathcal{C} is a cone $(L, (l_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ such that for every cone $(C, (f_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ there exists a unique morphisms h in $\mathcal{C}(C, L)$ such that for every object D in \mathcal{D} , $f_D = l_D \circ h$;

Considering the cone example in the category (\mathbb{R}, \leq) , while the cone will be the upper bound of the diagram, that is sequence, the limit will then be the least upper bound, the supremum.

The dual of the limit, the **colimit** under a diagram Σ_c in \mathcal{C} is represented as $(L, (l_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$;

Once again considering the category (\mathbb{R}, \leq) , the cocone was a lower bound, and hence the colimit will be the greatest lower bound, or infimum.

6.3 Examples of limits

The examples presented in this section will elaborate upon the fundamental constructions of the previous chapter, showing how some of these are limits and colimits. In all cases the underlying functor being considered is $F : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$.

6.3.1 Products and coproducts as limits and colimits

Consider a discrete category \mathcal{D} with only two objects A, B and morphisms being identities only. Let $\Sigma_{\mathcal{D}}$ be a diagram with vertices labeled by the objects in \mathcal{D} ,

$$A \quad B$$

Then the cone (C, f_A, f_B) over the diagram $\Sigma_C = F(\Sigma_D)$ in category \mathcal{C} is,

Then the limit, or universal cone, (L, l_A, l_B) over the diagram Σ_C in \mathcal{C} is,

This limit is precisely the definition of a product of the two objects FA, FB in \mathcal{C} . From this we can see that the colimit will be the coproduct of the two objects in \mathcal{C} .

6.3.2 Equalisers and coequalisers as limits and colimits.

Consider a category \mathcal{D} with two objects A, B and morphisms $\mathcal{D}(A, B) = \{u, v\}$. Let Σ_D be the following diagram,

Then the cone (C, f_A, f_B) over the diagram Σ_C , consists of an arrow into FA which makes equal the two maps Fu and Fv ,

The limit (L, l_A, l_B) over the diagram is,

$Fu \circ l_A = l_B \circ Fv$ then by the definition of an equaliser, (L, l_A) is an equaliser of morphisms Fu, Fv . Hence the equaliser is a limit and by the dual argument the coequaliser is a colimit.

6.3.3 Pullbacks and pushouts as limits

Let \mathcal{D} be a category where $\text{ob}(\mathcal{D}) = \{X, Y, Z\}$ with morphisms f in $\mathcal{D}(X, Y)$, g in $\mathcal{D}(Z, Y)$ and let Σ_D be the diagram,

Then the cone (C, f_X, f_Y, f_Z) over the diagram in category \mathcal{C} is,

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 C & \xrightarrow{f_X} & FX \\
 f_Z \downarrow & \searrow^{f_Y} & \downarrow Ff \\
 FZ & \xrightarrow{Fg} & FY
 \end{array}$$

The limit (L, l_X, l_Y, l_Z) over the diagram in \mathcal{C} is,

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 C & & & & \\
 \searrow^{f_X} & & & & \\
 & L & \xrightarrow{l_X} & FX & \\
 \downarrow f_Z & \downarrow l_Z & & \downarrow Ff & \\
 & FZ & \xrightarrow{Fg} & FY &
 \end{array}$$

To be precise we should have included the morphisms l_Y, f_Y , but excluding them reduces the complexity of the diagram and highlights the fact that the limit of the diagram in \mathcal{C} is the pullback (L, l_X, l_Z) of morphisms Ff, Fg . For the dual case, the colimit will be the pushout.

6.3.4 Limits and colimits as terminal and initial objects

Let D be an object of category \mathcal{D} and F a functor from \mathcal{D} to category \mathcal{C} . Then we can construct a category of cones over a diagram in \mathcal{C} , \mathbf{Cone}_D , with:

1. Objects: All cones $(C \in ob(\mathcal{C}), f_D)$ over a diagram in \mathcal{C} , where $f_D \in \mathcal{C}(C, FD)$.
2. Morphisms: For any pair of objects in \mathbf{Cone}_D a morphism in $\mathbf{Cone}_D((C, f_D), (C', f'_D))$ is a morphism $k \in \mathcal{C}(C, C')$ such that $f_D = f'_D \circ k$. That is, the following diagram commutes;

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 C & \xrightarrow{k} & C' \\
 f_D \downarrow & & \swarrow f'_D \\
 & & FD
 \end{array}$$

Since a limit is a universal cone, then a limit is also a terminal object in \mathbf{Cone}_D . By the dual argument we can construct a category of cocones under diagram Σ_D , in this case the colimit is an initial object.

6.4 Completeness

The discussion of completeness in the categorical sense has strong similarities to the concept of completeness in other branches of mathematics, for instance metric spaces. We know a metric space to be complete when every Cauchy sequence in the space has a limit, that is, converges to a point that exists within the space. This has a clear parallel to the definition of completeness below. In 8.1, we identify further similarities when we discuss adjoint functors and limits.

Definition 6.4.1. A category \mathcal{C} is *complete* when every small diagram in \mathcal{C} has a limit.

We can characterise completeness in terms of products and equalisers as the following theorem states.

Theorem 6.4.2. A category with equalisers and all small products is complete.

Proof. (See [15, Section V.2]). Let $\Sigma_{\mathcal{C}}$ be a diagram in \mathcal{C} , that is $F : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ transports $\Sigma_{\mathcal{D}}$ to $\Sigma_{\mathcal{C}} = F(\Sigma_{\mathcal{D}})$, and let \mathcal{C} have equalisers and small products. We begin by constructing a product of all objects of the codomains of the morphisms of the diagram, $(\prod_{f \in \text{mor}(\mathcal{D})} F(\text{codom } f), (p_f)_{f \in \text{mor}(\mathcal{D})})$. Let this new product be the product over all objects of the diagram in \mathcal{C} , $(\prod_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})} FA, (p_{\text{dom}(f)})_{f \in \text{mor}(\mathcal{D})})$, but this construction can be accomplished in two ways as shown by the commutative upper triangle and lower rectangle,

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 & & & & F(\text{codom } f) \\
 & & & & \uparrow p_f \\
 & & & p_{\text{codom } f} \nearrow & \\
 L & \xrightarrow{eq} & \prod_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})} FA & \xrightarrow[h']{h} & \prod_{f \in \text{mor}(\mathcal{D})} F(\text{codom } f) \\
 & \searrow l_A & \downarrow p_{\text{dom}(f)} & & \downarrow p_f \\
 & & F\text{dom}(f) & \xrightarrow{Ff} & F(\text{codom } f)
 \end{array}$$

Let (L, eq) be an equaliser of h and h' then $(L, (l_A)_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is also a cone over the diagram in \mathcal{C} since, for any morphism f in \mathcal{D} , $Ff \circ l_A = p_f \circ h' \circ eq = p_f \circ h \circ eq = p_{\text{codom } f} \circ eq$. That is, if we let $p_{\text{codom } f} \circ eq = l_{\text{codom } f}$ then $Ff \circ l_A = l_{\text{codom } f}$ as required. Also, as shown below, for any pair (Q, q) there is a unique morphism u , due to the universal properties of equaliser (L, eq) .

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 Q & & & & F(\text{codom } f) \\
 \downarrow u & \searrow q & & & \uparrow p_f \\
 L & \xrightarrow{eq} & \prod_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})} FA & \xrightarrow[h']{h} & \prod_{f \in \text{mor}(\mathcal{D})} F(\text{codom } f) \\
 & \searrow l_A & \downarrow p_{\text{dom}(f)} & & \downarrow p_f \\
 & & F\text{dom}(f) & \xrightarrow{Ff} & F(\text{codom } f)
 \end{array}$$

But $(Q, (q_A)_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is any other cone since if we let $q_A = p_{\text{dom}(f)} \circ q$ and let $q'_A = p_f \circ h \circ q = p_f \circ h' \circ q$, then $Ff \circ q_A = q'_A$. Finally $(L, (l_A)_{A \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is a universal cone since,

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & Q & \\
 q_A = p_{\text{dom}(f)} \circ q \swarrow & \exists! u \downarrow & \searrow q_{\text{codom } f} \\
 & L & \\
 l_A \swarrow & & \searrow l_{A'} \\
 F\text{dom}(f) & \xrightarrow{Ff} & F(\text{codom } f)
 \end{array}$$

$$l_A \circ u = p_{\text{dom}(f)} \circ (eq \circ u) = p_{\text{dom}(f)} \circ q = q_A. \quad \square$$

Chapter 7

Adjoint Functors

7.1 Motivations

Consider the case of adjoints of operators from linear algebra. For a linear operator $T : V \rightarrow W$ between vector spaces V and W , the adjoint operator $T^* : W^* \rightarrow V^*$ satisfies the equation,

$$(T^*f)(v) = f(Tv) \tag{7.1}$$

where $f : W \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ is a linear functional in W^* and v is a vector in V . Equivalently, this can be expressed as

$$T^* \circ f = f \circ T. \tag{7.2}$$

From equations 7.1 and 7.2 we see a direct relationship between a vector space and its dual, through the functional f . And so, what is revealed is a functional of the form $T^* \circ f : V \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ equated to a functional of the form $f \circ T : V \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$. This has a strong resemblance to the manner in which adjoint functors relate morphisms within different, non-isomorphic, categories. In [13], Mac Lane discusses other “strikingly parallel” properties between linear adjoints of operator algebra and adjoint functors. Palmquist, [17], goes further to prove that adjoint operators imply adjoint functors. Regardless of these apparent parallel properties mentioned, linear adjoint operators are limited to vector spaces. In contrast, adjoint functors can determine relationships between categories that are not the same, nor isomorphic, utilising the morphisms within categories.

7.2 Hom-set perspective

Definition 7.2.1. Let \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D} be categories and the family of morphisms of these categories be sets. Also, let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$, $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be functors. If for each object C in \mathcal{C} and each object D in \mathcal{D} there exists an isomorphism

$$\phi_{C,D} : \mathcal{D}(FC, D) \cong \mathcal{C}(C, GD) \tag{7.3}$$

natural in C and D , then F is left adjoint to G and G is right adjoint to F , expressed by the notation $F \dashv G$.

The naturality of $\phi_{C,D}$ in C and D implies that for any $f \in \mathcal{C}(C', C)$ and any $g \in \mathcal{D}(D, D')$

the following diagram commutes;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{D}(FC, D) & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C,D}} & \mathcal{C}(C, GD) \\ \mathcal{D}(Ff, g) \downarrow & & \downarrow \mathcal{C}(f, Gg) \\ \mathcal{D}(FC', D') & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C',D'}} & \mathcal{C}(C', GD') \end{array} \quad (7.4)$$

Here, $\mathcal{D}(Ff, g)$ is the set of morphisms from $\mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ to $\mathcal{D}(FC', D')$ where $Ff : FC' \rightarrow FC$ and $g : D \rightarrow D'$, we define $\mathcal{C}(f, Gg)$ similarly. We can illustrate this with the aid of the discussion in section 4.2, the natural transformation between functors $(-)^{**}$ and i , from $Vec_{\mathbb{K}} \rightarrow Vec_{\mathbb{K}}$. These two functors are naturally isomorphic and we can express this relationship with the analogous commutative diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V, U) & \xrightarrow{\eta_{V,U}} & Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V, U^{**}) \\ Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(f, g) \downarrow & & \downarrow Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(f, g^{**}) \\ Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V', U') & \xrightarrow{\eta_{V',U'}} & Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V', U'^{**}) \end{array} \quad (7.5)$$

Where, for any $f \in Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V, V')$ and $g \in Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(U, U')$, $i(V) = V, i(V') = V', i(f) = f$ and $(-)^{**}U = U^{**}, (-)^{**}U' = U'^{**}, (-)^{**}g = g^{**}$. We can represent the natural isomorphism between functors i and $(-)^{**}$ in the form of equation 7.3,

$$\eta_{V,U} : Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(iV, U) \cong Vec_{\mathbb{K}}(V, (-)^{**}U)$$

Back to the general case, we can also consider each component C and D of ϕ separately by letting $f^* = \mathcal{C}(-, GD)f$, $(Ff)^* = \mathcal{D}(-, D)Ff$, $g_* = \mathcal{D}(FC, -)g$ and $(Gg)_* = \mathcal{C}(C, -)Gg$ producing the following commutative diagrams;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{D}(FC, D) & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C,D}} & \mathcal{C}(C, GD) & \mathcal{D}(FC, D) & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C,D}} & \mathcal{C}(C, GD) \\ g_* \downarrow & & \downarrow (Gg)_* & (Ff)^* \downarrow & & \downarrow f^* \\ \mathcal{D}(FC, D') & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C,D'}} & \mathcal{C}(C, GD') & \mathcal{D}(FC', D) & \xrightarrow{\phi_{C',D}} & \mathcal{C}(C', GD) \end{array} \quad (7.6)$$

The isomorphism of (7.3) is also a natural isomorphism between functors,

$$\mathcal{D}(F-, -) : \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}, (C, D) \mapsto (FC, D) \mapsto \mathcal{D}(FC, D)$$

$$\mathcal{C}(-, G-) : \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}, (C, D) \mapsto (C, GD) \mapsto \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$$

then

$$\phi : \mathcal{D}(F-, -) \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}(-, G-) : \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$$

An alternative presentation of $F \dashv G$ is represented by the next diagram that is commutative up to natural isomorphism,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} & \xrightarrow{F^{op} \times 1_{\mathcal{D}}} & \mathcal{D}^{op} \times \mathcal{D} \\ \downarrow 1_{\mathcal{C}^{op}} \times G & \swarrow \phi & \downarrow \mathcal{D}(-, -) \\ \mathcal{C}^{op} \times \mathcal{C} & \xrightarrow{\mathcal{C}(-, -)} & \mathbf{Set} \end{array}$$

hence,

$$\mathcal{D}(-, -) \circ (F^{op} \times 1_{\mathcal{D}}) \cong \mathcal{C}(-, -) \circ (1_{\mathcal{C}^{op}} \times G).$$

7.3 Morphism only perspective

The previous section focused on Hom-Sets, but if we allow definition 7.2.1 to include categories with a class of morphisms that is larger than a set then we can apply another more general method for describing adjoint relations found in [15]; via the morphisms of a category directly. This approach will assist with the calculations of the next section. Although we are no longer restricted to Hom-Sets we can still use the diagrams of (7.6) to visually assist in the derivation of the equations below. Recall $f : C' \rightarrow C, g : D \rightarrow D'$ and let $h : FC \rightarrow D$ then we obtain the right adjunct of h , $\phi h : C \rightarrow GD$. The naturality conditions shown in (7.6) then become,

$$\phi(g \circ h) = Gg \circ \phi h, \quad (7.7)$$

$$\phi(h \circ Ff) = \phi h \circ f \quad (7.8)$$

for all h, f and g . To elaborate on these important formulae, given h and ϕh and exploiting the naturality conditions for objects C and D we can directly compute the right adjoints for objects C' and D' . That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(g \circ h : FC \rightarrow D') &= Gg \circ \phi h : C \rightarrow GD', \\ \phi(h \circ Ff : FC' \rightarrow D) &= \phi h \circ f : C' \rightarrow GD \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, if we let $j : C \rightarrow GD$ then $\phi^{-1}j : FC \rightarrow D$, the left adjunct of j . The naturality conditions then become,

$$\phi^{-1}(j \circ f) = \phi^{-1}j \circ Ff, \quad (7.9)$$

$$\phi^{-1}(Gg \circ j) = g \circ \phi^{-1}j \quad (7.10)$$

7.4 Unit and co-unit of adjunction

If we let $D = FC$ then equation (7.3) becomes $\phi_{C, FC} : \mathcal{D}(FC, FC) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(C, GFC)$. For any object C in category \mathcal{C} , we know that $1_{FC} \in \mathcal{D}(FC, FC)$ so we let $\eta_C = \phi_{C, FC}(1_{FC})$ then $\eta_C \in \mathcal{C}(C, GFC)$ and we can show that η_C is the component of a natural transformation, that is the following diagram commutes,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} C' & \xrightarrow{\eta_{C'}} & GFC' \\ f \downarrow & & \downarrow GFf \\ C & \xrightarrow{\eta_C} & GFC \end{array} \quad (7.11)$$

since,

$$\begin{aligned}
GFf \circ \eta_{C'} &= GFf \circ \phi_{C',FC'}(1_{FC'}) \\
&= \phi_{C',FC'}(Ff \circ 1_{FC'}) && \text{(by (7.7))} \\
&= \phi_{C',FC'}(Ff \circ F(1_{C'})) \\
&= \phi_{C',FC'}(F(f \circ 1_{C'})) \\
&= \phi_{C,FC}(F(1_C \circ f)) \\
&= \phi_{C,FC}(1_{FC} \circ Ff) \\
&= \phi_{C,FC}(1_{FC}) \circ f && \text{(by (7.8))} \\
&= \eta_C \circ f.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have the **unit of adjunction** $\eta : 1_C \Rightarrow GF$. Similarly, if we let $C = GD$ then equation (7.3) becomes $\phi_{GD,D} : \mathcal{D}(FGD, D) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(GD, GD)$ and if for any object D in \mathcal{D} we let $\varepsilon_D = \phi_{GD,D}^{-1}(1_{GD}) : FGD \rightarrow D$ then by (7.9) and (7.10),

$$\begin{aligned}
\varepsilon_{D'} \circ FGg &= \phi_{GD',D'}^{-1}(1_{GD'}) \circ FGg \\
&= \phi_{GD',D'}^{-1}(1_{GD'} \circ Gg) \\
&= \phi_{GD',D'}^{-1}(G(1_{D'}) \circ Gg) \\
&= \phi_{GD',D'}^{-1}(G(1_{D'} \circ g)) \\
&= \phi_{GD,D}^{-1}(G(g \circ 1_D)) \\
&= \phi_{GD,D}^{-1}(Gg \circ 1_{GD}) \\
&= g \circ \phi_{GD,D}^{-1}(1_{GD}) \\
&= g \circ \varepsilon_D.
\end{aligned}$$

That is, the following square commutes

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
FGD & \xrightarrow{\varepsilon_D} & D \\
FGg \downarrow & & \downarrow g \\
FGD' & \xrightarrow{\varepsilon_{D'}} & D'
\end{array} \tag{7.12}$$

and hence $\varepsilon_D : FGD \rightarrow D$ is a component of the natural transformation $\varepsilon : FG \Rightarrow 1_{\mathcal{D}}$, the **co-unit of adjunction**.

7.5 Universal morphism perspective

A universal morphism, known as a Universal Arrow in [15] and as a Reflection in [5], is an alternative and insightful manner in which to describe adjoint functors as will be demonstrated in the examples of section 8.4. Knowing in advance that a category contains a particular universal morphism can aid in determining if two functors form an adjoint pair. Conversely by finding an adjoint pair we will find a universal morphism, that may or may not have been previously identified as such. A universal morphism is defined in the following manner.

Definition 7.5.1. Let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ be a functor and X an object in \mathcal{D} . The morphism u in $\mathcal{D}(X, FC)$ is universal if and only if for every morphism b in $\mathcal{D}(X, FC')$ there exists a unique

morphism a in $\mathcal{C}(C, C')$ such that $b = Fa \circ u$.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{u} & FC \\ & \searrow b & \downarrow Fa \\ & & FC' \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} C \\ \downarrow \exists! a \\ C' \end{array}$$

7.5.1 Left adjoint

We can now define a left adjoint in terms of a universal morphism, here the universal morphisms are components of a natural transformation.

Definition 7.5.2. Let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ and $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be functors with objects C in \mathcal{C} and D in \mathcal{D} . If there exists a natural transformation $\eta : 1_{\mathcal{C}} \Rightarrow GF$ such that for every object C and any morphism $b \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ there exists a unique morphism $a \in \mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ such that the following triangle commutes,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} C & \xrightarrow{\eta_C} & GFC \\ & \searrow b & \downarrow Ga \\ & & GD \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} FC \\ \downarrow \exists! a \\ D \end{array} \quad (7.13)$$

then F is left adjoint to G , $a : FC \rightarrow D$ is the left adjunct of $b = Ga \circ \eta_C : C \rightarrow GD$ and η is the unit of adjunction.

7.5.2 Right adjoint

The right adjoint can be defined using a co-universal morphism.

Definition 7.5.3. Let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ and $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be functors with objects C in \mathcal{C} and D in \mathcal{D} . If there exists a natural transformation $\epsilon : FG \Rightarrow 1_{\mathcal{D}}$ such that for every object D and any morphism $a \in \mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ there exists a unique morphism $b \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ such that the following triangle commutes,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} D & \xleftarrow{\epsilon_D} & FGD \\ & \swarrow a & \uparrow Fb \\ & & FC \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} GD \\ \uparrow \exists! b \\ C \end{array} \quad (7.14)$$

then G is right adjoint to F .

7.6 Combining Adjoint Definitions

Proposition 7.6.1. Let $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ and $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be functors. Then the following are equivalent;

1. F is left adjoint to G , symbolically $F \dashv G$.
2. For each object C in \mathcal{C} and D in \mathcal{D} there exists an isomorphism

$$\phi_{C,D} : \mathcal{D}(FC, D) \cong \mathcal{C}(C, GD) \quad (7.15)$$

natural in C and D .

3. There exists a natural transformation $\eta : 1_{\mathcal{C}} \Rightarrow GF$ such that for every object C in \mathcal{C} and every morphism $b \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ there exists a unique morphism $a \in \mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ such that

the following triangle commutes, $b = Ga \circ \eta_C (= \phi_{C,D}(a))$

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 C & \xrightarrow{\eta_C} & GFC \\
 & \searrow b & \downarrow Ga \\
 & & GD
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{ccc}
 FC & & \\
 \downarrow \exists! a & & \\
 D & &
 \end{array}
 \quad \text{And}
 \tag{7.16}$$

4. There exists a natural transformations $\epsilon : FG \Rightarrow 1_{\mathcal{D}}$ such that for every object D in \mathcal{D} and every morphism $a \in \mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ there exists a unique morphism $b \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ such that the following triangle commutes, $a = \epsilon_D \circ Fb (= \phi_{C,D}^{-1}(b))$

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 D & \xleftarrow{\epsilon_D} & FGD \\
 & \swarrow a & \uparrow Fb \\
 & & FC
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{ccc}
 GD & & \\
 \uparrow \exists! b & & \\
 C & &
 \end{array}
 \tag{7.17}$$

5. G is right adjoint to F

Proof. (1. \Leftrightarrow 2.) By definition 7.2.1 but, let the class of morphisms be a set or larger.

(2. \Rightarrow 3. & 2. \Rightarrow 4.) Suppose the isomorphism (7.15) exists then, as was shown in section 7.4, by letting $D = FC$ and $C = GD$ we obtain the unit and counit of adjunction, respectively; $\eta : 1_C \Rightarrow GF$ and $\epsilon : FG \Rightarrow 1_{\mathcal{D}}$. Now for any morphism a in $\mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ there exists a $\phi(a)$ in $\mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ and Ga in $\mathcal{C}(GFC, GD)$, but $Ga \circ \eta_C = Ga \circ \phi_{C,FC}(a \circ 1_{FC}) = \phi_{C,FC}(a \circ 1_{FC}) = \phi_{C,FC}(a)$ using equation (7.7). Let $\phi_{C,FC}(a) = b$ and we have the commutative triangle (7.16). Similarly, by considering the co-unit of adjunction, we can derive the commutative triangle (7.17).

(3. \Rightarrow 2.) Suppose part 3 is satisfied. Since for every morphism b in $\mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ there exists a unique morphism a in $\mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ then we can construct a morphism ϕ from $\mathcal{D}(FC, D)$ to $\mathcal{C}(C, GD)$, which has an inverse morphism, hence is an isomorphism. The naturality of $\phi_{C,D}$ in C and D was discussed in section 7.2 and was expressed diagrammatically as shown in diagram (7.6). Showing the commutativity of the first diagram, we follow the logic shown in [3]; for any morphism a in $\mathcal{D}(FC, D)$, g in $\mathcal{D}(D, D')$ and f in $\mathcal{C}(C', C)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (Gg)_* \circ \phi_{C,D}(a) &= (Gg)_* \circ (Ga \circ \eta_C) \\
 &= (Gg) \circ (Ga \circ \eta_C) \\
 &= G(g \circ a) \circ \eta_C \\
 &= \phi_{C,D'}(g \circ a) && \text{since } g \circ a \text{ is in } \mathcal{D}(FC, D') \\
 &= \phi_{C,D'}(g_*(a))
 \end{aligned}$$

For the commutativity of the second rectangle;

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^* \circ \phi_{C,D}(a) &= f^* \circ (Ga \circ \eta_C) \\
 &= (Ga \circ \eta_C) \circ f \\
 &= Ga \circ (n_C \circ f) \\
 &= Ga \circ (GFf \circ n_{C'}) && \text{see commutative rectangle (7.16)} \\
 &= G(a \circ Ff) \circ \eta_{C'} \\
 &= \phi_{C',D}(a \circ Ff) \\
 &= \phi_{C',D}((Ff)^*(a))
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, ϕ is natural in C and D .

(4. \Rightarrow 2.) Duality. Suppose part 4 is true. Since part 4 is the dual of part 3 then, by the duality principle, we are done.

(3. \Leftrightarrow 4.) Duality. Part 4 is the dual of part 3.

(3. \Leftrightarrow 1.) By definition 7.5.2.

(4. \Leftrightarrow 5.) By definition 7.5.3.

□

Chapter 8

The Freyd Adjoint Functor Theorem

This chapter represents the focal point of this paper. The previous chapters have been discussed and developed in an effort to ensure the reader gains a clear understanding of the main theorem to be presented, with an appreciation for the convergence and interplay of the concepts and definitions from the preceding chapters. This chapter will focus on the existence of adjoints from the perspective of Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem, for other existence theorems, including the Special Adjoint Functor Theorem, the reader is directed to texts such as [15] or [5]. Section 8.1 will present the concept of limit preservation and its relationship to adjoints, section 8.2 will discuss a specific comma category in the light of limit preservation and section 8.3 will state the main theorem and its proof, incorporating the concepts of sections 8.1 and 8.2. The final two sections utilise Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem to present examples and applications of the theorem. Section 8.4 presents examples of identifying left adjoints, using Freyd's theorem, while in section 8.5 left adjoints uncover established important properties in various fields of mathematics, highlighting the universality of category theory and adjoint functors and we also gain a deeper understanding of the limits that surface within these specific domains.

8.1 Adjoints and limit preservation

As we shall see in this chapter, from the the Freyd adjoint functor theorem we not only have a criteria to identify if a functor has a left adjoint, but we also discover that knowing an adjunction exists then limits are preserved. This result leads us to identifying non-trivial and interesting limits for categories. The following definition introduces the notion of what it means for a functor to preserve limits.

Definition 8.1.1. Given a functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ and any limit $(L, (l_B)_{B \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{B})})$ over some diagram $\Sigma_{\mathcal{C}}$ (the image of any functor $G : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$) in \mathcal{C} . F will preserve limits if and only if $(FL, (Fl_B)_{B \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{B})})$, over diagram $F(\Sigma_{\mathcal{C}})$, is a limit in \mathcal{D} .

We saw an example of limit preservation in the introduction, when considering \mathbb{R} and the derived category (\mathbb{R}, \geq) . Consider the functor $F : (\mathbb{R}, \geq) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}, \geq)$ and a sequence of real numbers in the domain, as a diagram. Let the the sequence converge to a real number d , the limit over the diargam. Then, if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(x_n) = F(d)$$

whenever,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = d$$

then F preserves limits.

In the specific case of small limits, a functor is known as **continuous** when it preserves all small limits. With theorem 6.4.2, this leads to the following definition.

Definition 8.1.2. A functor is continuous if and only if it preserves all small products and equalizers.

The following theorem shows that functors with a left adjoint preserve limits, this fact will be used in the proof of the main theorem. The proof of the following theorem is attributed to [5, Section 3.2].

Theorem 8.1.3. *If a functor $F : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}$ has a left adjoint then F preserves all limits that exist in \mathcal{A} .*

Proof. Suppose $G : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ is left adjoint to $F : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}$. For a functor $H : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$, suppose $(L, (p_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is a limit of H . If we can prove that $(FL, (Fp_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is a limit of $F \circ H$ then we are done. To this end; consider a cone $(B, (q_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ over $F \circ H$,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & B & \\ q_D \swarrow & & \searrow q_{D'} \\ FHD & \xrightarrow{FHd} & FHD' \end{array}$$

Since G is left adjoint to F , then by part 2 of 7.6.1, there exists an isomorphism

$$\phi_{B,HD} : \mathcal{A}(GB, HD) \cong \mathcal{B}(B, FHD)$$

natural in B and HD . Then the morphism $q_D : B \rightarrow FHD$ corresponds to a morphism $r_D : GB \rightarrow HD$. Also, the naturality of $\phi_{B,HD}$ implies the following diagram commutes,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{A}(GB, HD) & \xrightarrow{\phi_{B,HD}} & \mathcal{B}(B, FHD) \\ \mathcal{A}(1_{GB}, Hd) \downarrow & & \downarrow \mathcal{B}(1_B, FHd) \\ \mathcal{A}(GB, HD') & \xrightarrow{\phi_{B,HD'}} & \mathcal{B}(B, FHD') \end{array}$$

Then, given the isomorphism and the naturality of $\phi_{B,HD}$;

$$\begin{aligned} r_{D'} &= \phi_{B,HD'}^{-1}(q_{D'}) \\ &= \phi_{B,HD'}^{-1}(FHd \circ q_D) \\ &= (\phi_{B,HD'}^{-1} \circ \mathcal{B}(1_B, FHd))(q_D) \\ &= (\mathcal{A}(1_{GB}, HD) \circ \phi_{B,HD}^{-1})(q_D) \\ &= \mathcal{A}(1_{GB}, HD)(r_D) \\ &= Hd \circ r_D. \end{aligned}$$

Then $(GB, (r_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is a cone over H . And we get a unique factorisation $r : GB \rightarrow L$ such that for each $D \in \mathcal{D}$, $p_D \circ r = r_D$. But, the morphism r corresponds to a morphism $s = \phi_{L,B}(r) : B \rightarrow FL$ in \mathcal{B} . Repeating the naturality argument above for the the isomorphism $\phi_{L,B}$, we find $Fp_D \circ s = q_D$ for unique s ;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & B & \\ & \exists! s \downarrow & \\ & FL & \\ q_D \swarrow & & \searrow q_{D'} \\ FHD & \xrightarrow{FHd} & FHD' \\ & \uparrow Fp_D \quad \uparrow Fp_{D'} & \end{array}$$

Hence, $(FL, (Fp_D)_{D \in \text{ob}(\mathcal{D})})$ is a limit of $F \circ H$. \square

In a similar manner we can prove the dual of this theorem: If a functor has a right adjoint then that functor preserves all small colimits.

From the preceding theorem we see another parallel between adjoint functors and topology. Specifically, a function between two metric spaces, $f : M \rightarrow M'$, is called continuous whenever f preserves the limits in M , [1]. In the case of metric spaces, the limits are points in the metric space upon which a sequence converges.

8.2 A comma category

There are a variety of comma categories, as presented in [15], but to prove the main theorem we only need to concentrate on the following.

Definition 8.2.1. Let $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be a functor. For any object C in \mathcal{C} the comma category, G under C , denoted $(C \downarrow G)$, consists of:

1. Objects: pairs (D, f) where D is in $\text{ob}(\mathcal{D})$ and $f \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$.
2. Morphisms: $g : (D, f) \rightarrow (D', f')$ when $g \in \mathcal{D}(D, D')$ such that $f' = Gg \circ f$ as shown by the commutative diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & C & \\ f \swarrow & & \searrow f' \\ GD & \xrightarrow{Gg} & GD' \end{array}$$

The dual of this comma category is $(G \downarrow C)$, known as the comma category G over C , as can be appreciated when the arrows are reversed in the above definition. The main theorem will use the properties of $(C \downarrow G)$ in its proof, but we can only use it if $(C \downarrow G)$ is a complete category. The following lemma and proof will ensure we can use this comma category.

Lemma 8.2.2. *Let \mathcal{D} be a complete category. If the functor $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ preserves limits then, for every object C in \mathcal{C} , the comma category $(C \downarrow G)$ is complete.*

Proof. Recall the completeness theorem 6.4.2, then it is enough to show that the comma category $(C \downarrow G)$ has small products and equalisers.

Suppose \mathcal{D} is complete then there exists the small product $(\prod_{i \in I} D_i, p_i \in \mathcal{D}(\prod_{i \in I} D_i, D_i))$ in \mathcal{D} indexed by some set I . By the universal properties of a product, for any other D with morphisms to $\prod_{i \in I} D_i$ and D_i there exists a unique morphism h as shown in the commutative diagram,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} D & \xrightarrow{\exists! h} & \prod_{i \in I} D_i \\ & \searrow g_i & \downarrow p_i \\ & & D_i \end{array}$$

But G preserves limits, that is small products are preserved, then $(G \prod_{i \in I} D_i, Gp_i)$ is a product in \mathcal{C} . If we draw a cone over the product diagram in \mathcal{C} then we have the following objects in

$(C \downarrow G); (D, f_D), (\prod_{i \in I} D_i, f_\Pi)$ and (D_i, f_{D_i})

with morphisms;

But h in $(C \downarrow G)$ is unique since h in \mathcal{D} is unique. Therefore, small products exist in $(C \downarrow G)$. For the equaliser; given \mathcal{D} is complete then there exists an equaliser (Z, eq) of the morphisms $f, g \in \mathcal{D}(D, D')$ represented by the commutative diagram,

Since G preserves limits then $(GZ, G(eq))$ is an equaliser of morphisms Gf and Gg . Consider the following diagram as it will assist in the remainder of the proof;

Form a cone over the equaliser diagram of $(GZ, G(eq))$, then $Gf \circ u = Gg \circ u = v$ and $h \in \mathcal{C}(C, GZ)$ is unique (by the properties of equalisers). From this $eq: (Z, h) \rightarrow (D, u)$ is a unique morphism in $(C \downarrow G)$. Also, the diagram shows that (D, u) and (D', v) are objects in $(C \downarrow G)$ so let $f, g: (D, u) \rightarrow (D', v)$ be two morphisms in $(C \downarrow G)$. We now have,

$$(Z, h) \xrightarrow{eq} (D, u) \begin{matrix} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{matrix} (D', v)$$

The final step is to show that eq is an equaliser in $(C \downarrow G)$. To this end, consider another object (W, k) and morphism $w: (W, k) \rightarrow (D, u)$ in $(C \downarrow G)$

But we know in \mathcal{D} ; $f \circ w = g \circ w$, $w = eq \circ r$ and $r \in \mathcal{D}(W, Z)$ is unique and since $Gr \circ k = h$ forms the required commutative triangle in comma category $(C \downarrow G)$ then $r : (W, k) \rightarrow (Z, h)$ is a unique morphism in $(C \downarrow G)$ therefore eq is an equaliser in $(C \downarrow G)$. \square

8.3 The theorem

Before we state and prove the main theorem we need a final lemma, the proof of which is a combination of [15, Section V.6] and [3, Section 9.8]. This lemma will assist in showing that the unit of adjunction is in fact an initial object in $(C \downarrow G)$.

Lemma 8.3.1. *Let \mathcal{C} be a complete category and locally small. \mathcal{C} has an initial object if and only if it satisfies the following solution set condition: there exists a set of objects $(C_i)_{i \in I}$ in \mathcal{C} , indexed by set I , such that for every object C in \mathcal{C} there exists an $i \in I$ and a morphism $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}(C_i, C)$.*

Proof. We begin with the observation that if \mathcal{C} has an initial object then we can form the singleton set with the initial object as the set's only member, this satisfies the condition. For the converse, first assume the solution set condition is satisfied. Since \mathcal{C} is complete we can construct a product of all of the elements C_i , let this product be W . Thus we have projection morphisms, $pr_i \in \mathcal{C}(W, C_i)$ for each $i \in I$ and so by assumption there exists an element $\phi = \gamma \circ pr_i \in \mathcal{C}(W, C)$ for every object C in \mathcal{C} . As this set of morphisms is not necessarily singleton for every object C , we call W "weakly initial". Now consider the set of morphisms $\mathcal{C}(W, W)$ and construct an equaliser (V, eq) as;

$$V \xrightarrow{eq} W \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{1_W} \\ \xrightarrow{h_W} \end{array} W$$

From this equaliser,

$$h_W \circ eq = 1_W \circ eq = eq \circ 1_V \quad (8.1)$$

and $\psi = \phi \circ eq \in \mathcal{C}(V, C)$, assuming ψ is not unique then there exists two morphisms $f, g \in \mathcal{C}(V, C)$ and construct the equaliser (U, eq_1)

$$U \xrightarrow{eq_1} V \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} C$$

For clarity we can combine the necessary morphisms into a single diagram;

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} U & \xrightarrow{eq_1} & V & \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} & C \\ \uparrow j & & \downarrow eq & & \uparrow \gamma \\ W & \xrightarrow{1_W} & W & \xrightarrow{pr_i} & C_i \end{array}$$

Since W is weakly initial then there exists a $j \in \mathcal{C}(W, U)$. By equation (8.1), for endomorphisms of W ,

$$\begin{aligned} (eq \circ eq_1 \circ j) \circ eq &= 1_W \circ eq \quad \text{and} \\ eq \circ (eq_1 \circ j \circ eq) &= eq \circ 1_V \end{aligned}$$

But since the equaliser (V, eq) is a monomorphism, see section 5.4.1, then

$$eq_1 \circ j \circ eq = 1_V$$

and $(eq_1 \circ j \circ eq) \circ eq_1 = eq_1$ that is, $eq_1 \circ (j \circ eq \circ eq_1) = eq_1 \circ 1_U$ then

$$j \circ eq \circ eq_1 = 1_U$$

since eq_1 is an equaliser and a monomorphism. From this we determine $U \simeq V$ and eq_1 has an inverse, then $(f \circ eq_1) \circ eq_1^{-1} = (g \circ eq_1) \circ eq_1^{-1} \Rightarrow f = g$. Therefore V is initial. \square

We are now in the position to state and prove the main theorem, see [15, Section V.6].

Main Theorem (Freyd Adjoint Functor Theorem). *Let \mathcal{D} be a locally small complete category. The functor $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ has a left adjoint if and only if it preserves all small limits and, for every object C in \mathcal{C} , the following solution set condition is satisfied: there exists a set $\{S_i$ in $\mathcal{D} | i \in I\}$ and $\{f_i$ in $\mathcal{C}(C, GS_i) | i \in I\}$ such that for every object D in \mathcal{D} and every morphism $b \in \mathcal{C}(C, GD)$ there exists a single $i \in I$ and morphism $a \in \mathcal{D}(S_i, D)$ such that the following triangle commutes,*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} C & \xrightarrow{f_i} & GS_i \\ & \searrow b & \downarrow Ga \\ & & GD \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} S_i \\ \downarrow \exists! a \\ D \end{array} \quad (8.2)$$

Proof. Suppose the functor $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ has a left adjoint then by theorem 8.1.3, G preserves limits. Now let the functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ be left adjoint to G then by 3 of proposition 7.6.1 there exists a unit of adjunction $\eta : 1_{\mathcal{C}} \Rightarrow GF$ such that for every object C in \mathcal{C} there exists the universal morphism $\eta_C : C \rightarrow GFC$. If we let $\{S_i\} = \{FC\}$ and $\{f_i\} = \{\eta_C\}$ then the solution set condition is satisfied for this singleton set. Conversely, if we consider the morphisms and objects of the comma category $(C \downarrow G)$,

in \mathcal{C}

in $(C \downarrow G)$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} C & \xrightarrow{f_i} & GS_i \\ & \searrow f' & \downarrow Gg \\ & & GD' \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} S_i \\ \downarrow g \\ D' \end{array} \quad (S_i, f_i) \xrightarrow{g} (D', f')$$

then in order for G to have a left adjoint we require morphisms f to have the properties of the unit of adjunction, the components of which for every C will be $f_i \in \mathcal{C}(C, GS_i)$, where (S_i, f_i) is an initial object in $(C \downarrow G)$. In order to use the category $(C \downarrow G)$ as the basis of this proof we must ensure it is locally small, complete and it satisfies the solution set condition of Lemma 8.3.1. Referring to the diagram above, since \mathcal{D} is locally small then the commutative triangle in \mathcal{C} can only be satisfied by a set of morphisms in \mathcal{C} , hence $(C \downarrow G)$ must be locally small. By lemma 8.2.2, since by assumption $G : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ preserves limits and D is complete then $(C \downarrow G)$ is complete. Assume the solution set condition of this theorem has been satisfied, then by the resultant commutative triangle

$$\begin{array}{ccc} C & \xrightarrow{f_i} & GS_i \\ & \searrow f' & \downarrow Gg \\ & & GD' \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} S_i \\ \downarrow \exists! g \\ D' \end{array}$$

we have a set of objects, $\{(S_i, f_i \in \mathcal{C}(C, GS_i)) | i \in I\}$ in $(C \downarrow G)$, such that for every object (D', f') there exists a single morphism $g : (S_i, f_i) \rightarrow (D', f')$ for each $i \in I$, since g is unique to f' in \mathcal{C} . Then by Lemma 8.3.1, there exists an initial object. Now, by assumption, for every object C there exists an S_i in \mathcal{D} then, for a functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$, let $FC = S_i$ for some $i \in I$.

We now have an initial object $(FC, f_i \in \mathcal{C}(C, GFC))$ where f_i is universal. Finally, we need to show that f_i is the component of a natural transformation for every object C , that is f_i is the component of the unit of adjunction; let $D' = FC'$ and $h \in \mathcal{C}(C, C')$ then the following square commutes since by the universality of f_i , $GFh \circ f_i = f' = f_{C'} \circ h$.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 C & \xrightarrow{f_i} & GFC \\
 h \downarrow & \searrow f' & \downarrow GFh \\
 C' & \xrightarrow{f_{C'}} & GFC'
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 FC \\
 \downarrow \exists! g \\
 FC'
 \end{array}$$

Therefore, G has a left adjoint. □

8.4 Examples

8.4.1 $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ and Set

Consider the forgetful functor $U : Vec_{\mathbb{F}} \rightarrow Set$. $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ is a locally small and complete category, but to show the latter, we can apply theorem 6.4.2; the product of objects in $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ is the direct product of vectors spaces, which we know is a vector space, while an equaliser in $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$

$$Z \xrightarrow{\iota} V \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} W$$

is the vector space $\{v \in V | f(v) = g(v)\}$, where V is a vector space and f, g are linear transformations and ι is the inclusion map from a subspace of V . Hence, by Theorem 6.4.2, $Vec_{\mathbb{F}}$ is complete.

To show that U is continuous, we only need to show that all small products and equalisers are preserved, by definition 8.1.2. When we forget the vector space structure of the direct product then we are left with the underlying set of a cartesian product, hence small products are preserved by U . Similarly, forgetting the vector space structure of the equaliser leaves a set $\{v \in V | f(v) = g(v)\}$, where V is now a set and f, g are functions. Hence the equalisers are preserved by U .

For the solution set condition, we consider the following. For every object X in **Set**, there is a vector space V_X , where the elements of X form basis vectors in V_X . Let $f_X : X \rightarrow UV_X$ be the function that sends each $x \in X$ to itself, but where in V_X it is considered as a basis vector. For any other vector space W , we also have a function $g : X \rightarrow UW$, which will be in 1-1 correspondence with a function $h : V_X \rightarrow W$. This is the case since we can map the basis vectors to elements in W . This leads to the commutativity of the triangle below since; for any basis vector $b_x \in V_X$ that maps to a $w \in W$, when forgetting the vector space structure, that b_x is simply x of X . Diagrammatically,

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 X & \xrightarrow{f_X} & UV_X \\
 & \searrow g & \downarrow Uh \\
 & & UW
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 V_X \\
 \downarrow \exists! h \\
 W
 \end{array}$$

Hence, by the Freyd Adjoint Functor Theorem, U has a left adjoint.

8.4.2 Free Groups

Consider the forgetful functor $U : \mathbf{Grp} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$, where the group structure is forgotten, mapping groups to their underlying set and homomorphisms to functions. We can show that the functor

U has a left adjoint using Freyd's theorem. First, we note that **Grp** is locally small and complete. U will clearly preserve limits, since any limit within a group object of **Grp** will reside in the underlying set of that group. Hence, the domain of U has forgotten the group structure and retains the structure of the underlying set. For the solution set condition; for each X in **Set**, consider any function $g : X \rightarrow UG$, for any group G , which factors through the subgroup G' of G . That is, g is the composition of the morphisms $X \rightarrow UG' \rightarrow UG$. G' is generated by all elements $g(x)$ so every element in G' is a finite product of generators and their inverses, of the form

$$g(x_1)^{\epsilon_1} \cdots g(x_n)^{\epsilon_n} \quad \text{where } \epsilon_i \in \{-1, 1\},$$

and the cardinality of G' is bounded by $\max(|X|, \aleph_0)^1$. Then, we arrive at a solution set for U at X by considering all maps $X \rightarrow UH_i$, where each H_i is a group with cardinality at most $\max(|X|, \aleph_0)$. We see that the triangle below commutes since, like G' , g will factor through each group H .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f_i} & UH_i & & H_i \\ & \searrow g & \downarrow Ua & & \downarrow \exists!a \\ & & UG & & G \end{array}$$

Hence, U has a left adjoint. If we now consider the functor discussed in section 3.2.5, $F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Grp}$, the free group FX on some set X satisfies the solution set condition, that is $H_i = FX$. Then, F is left adjoint to U .

This example serves to highlight the universality of the categorical approach, as we see in [20], a consequence of the Adjoint Functor Theorem is the existence of free objects, including free groups, when a forgetful functor has a left adjoint. But we also find that tensor products, completions and Čech compactifications are also immediate from Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem.

8.4.3 Exponential law for sets

For this example, consider any set Y and let us define the following functor:

$$\begin{aligned} (-^Y) : \mathbf{Set} &\rightarrow \mathbf{Set} \\ Z &\mapsto (-^Y)Z = Z^Y \quad (\text{set of all functions from set } Y \text{ to } Z) \\ (g : Z \rightarrow Z') &\mapsto (-^Y)g : Z^Y \rightarrow Z'^Y, f \mapsto g \circ f \end{aligned}$$

Applying Freyd's Theorem to determine if this functor has a left adjoint; first, we know **Set** is locally small. Next, does this functor preserve small limits? To answer this, consider a limit (L, l) in **Set** over some diagram and also consider any cone, (X, p) , over the same diagram. We know that there must exist a unique morphism $h : X \rightarrow L$, since L is a limit. Now $((-^Y)L = L^Y, (-^Y)l = l^Y)$ and (X^Y, p^Y) are both cones. Also, $(-^Y)h : X^Y \rightarrow L^Y$ is unique since h is, hence small limits have been preserved by $(-^Y)$. To satisfy the solution set condition, consider any sets X, Y, Z and a function

$$f(x, y) : X \times Y \rightarrow Z.$$

If we fix an element of the domain $x' \in X$ then

$$f(x', y) : Y \rightarrow Z \in Z^Y.$$

¹That is, the maximum between the cardinality of X and the cardinality of the natural numbers.

If we now let x' vary over X then we have a function

$$\eta_x : X \rightarrow Z^Y.$$

If we replace Z in the codomain of η_x with the set $X \times Y$, then we have the function $\eta_x : X \rightarrow (X \times Y)^Y$. This shows that for any set X we can find a mapping $X \rightarrow (X \times Y)^Y$ for any set Y . Also, for any other set W we can follow the same process, but begin with a function $h(x, y) : X \times Y \rightarrow W$, which will lead to a function $\gamma_x : X \rightarrow W^Y$ and we note that γ_x is derived from $h(x, y)$ and so they are unique to each other. Now we can form the following commutative triangle,

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{\eta_x} & (-^Y)(X \times Y) & & X \times Y \\ & \searrow \gamma_x & \downarrow (-^Y)h & & \downarrow \exists!h \\ & & (-^Y)W & & W \end{array}$$

Hence, $(-^Y)$ has a left adjoint by Freyd's theorem. But note,

$$(X \times Y)^Y = (-^Y)(X \times Y) = (-^Y)(- \times Y)X$$

then by proposition 7.6.1, part 3, we see that the functor $(- \times Y)$, defined by

$$\begin{aligned} - \times Y : \mathbf{Set} &\rightarrow \mathbf{Set}, \\ X &\mapsto (- \times Y)X = X \times Y \\ (g : X \rightarrow X') &\mapsto (- \times Y)g : X \times Y \rightarrow X' \times Y, (x, y) \mapsto (g(x), y), \end{aligned}$$

is left adjoint to $(-^Y)$. Then, by part 2 of the same proposition, we have the natural isomorphism

$$\mathbf{Set}((- \times Y)X, Z) \cong \mathbf{Set}(X, (-^Y)Z)$$

that is

$$\mathbf{Set}(X \times Y, Z) \cong \mathbf{Set}(X, Z^Y)$$

or

$$Z^{X \times Y} \cong (Z^Y)^X$$

which we know as the exponential law for sets.

8.5 Further illustrative examples

8.5.1 Quantifiers

The discovery by Lawvere that the quantifiers, \exists and \forall , are adjoints to a functor had a profound impact to algebraic logic in the 1960s. Without going into the details of algebraic logic we present a less formal justification, found in [25], for a more detailed discussion consult [3].

Let X be a set and denote $\mathcal{P}(X)$ for the power set of X . We can form a partially ordered set, or poset, $(\mathcal{P}(X), \leq)$ by applying an ordering on the subsets of X such that, if $S \subseteq T \subseteq X$ then $S \leq T$. Now, as discussed in 2.4.2, we can construct a category from $(\mathcal{P}(X), \leq)$ by letting the objects to be the subsets of X and for any subsets S, T of X there will be a single morphism between them when $S \subseteq T$. Consider any function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and any set V such that $V \subseteq Y$ then

$$f^{-1}(V) = \{x \in X | f(x) \in V\}$$

then $f^{-1} : \mathcal{P}(Y) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)$, where we apply pre-ordering on the subsets of X and Y , f^{-1} is a

functor. Now define the following functors for any $U \subseteq X$;

$$\begin{aligned}\exists_f : \mathcal{P}(X) &\rightarrow \mathcal{P}(Y), \quad \exists_f U = \{y \in Y \mid \exists x \in f^{-1}(y) \text{ such that } x \in U\} \\ \forall_f : \mathcal{P}(X) &\rightarrow \mathcal{P}(Y), \quad \forall_f U = \{y \in Y \mid \forall x \in f^{-1}(y), x \in U\}\end{aligned}$$

$\exists_f \dashv f^{-1}$ and $f^{-1} \dashv \forall_f$, then f^{-1} has a left and right adjoint. The functors \exists_f and \forall_f represent the quantifiers \exists and \forall .

A consequence of the Adjoint Functor Theorem is that f^{-1} will preserve small limits, since it has a left adjoint. We know that a product is a limit, but as we see in [26, Section 6.1] limits in preordered sets are meets, which are identified with \wedge and if we consider the definition of meets in [25, Section 3.4], which is apt since the addition of anti-symmetry to posets does not remove the similarity between products of preorders and posets, we can interpret this as a small arbitrary product $(S \wedge T, f_S, f_T)$ in $\mathcal{P}(Y)$;

Then for any other small product (Q, q_S, q_T) in $\mathcal{P}(Y)$, there exists a unique $h : Q \rightarrow S \wedge T$, that is, $Q \leq S \wedge T$. Also, $S \wedge T \leq S$ and $S \wedge T \leq T$, hence $S \wedge T$ is the greatest lower bound, infimum, in $\mathcal{P}(Y)$. Since f^{-1} preserves limits, then the infimum of $\mathcal{P}(Y)$ is mapped to the infimum of $\mathcal{P}(X)$. Hence, f^{-1} is order preserving, that is for any $W, W' \in \mathcal{P}(Y)$ where $W \leq W'$, $f^{-1}(W) \leq f^{-1}(W')$.

8.5.2 Propositional logic

Propositional logic is another area where adjoints arise naturally and we find an excellent example in [24], but in the following we will extend this example further and apply the Freyd Adjoint Functor Theorem to derive the *exportation rule of replacement*;

$$((S \wedge P) \rightarrow Q) \leftrightarrow (S \rightarrow (P \rightarrow Q))$$

Before commencing the example, let us consider some basic theory. Let P and Q be valid propositions, we only need two logical connectives for this example; conjunction \wedge and implication, \rightarrow . We also require;

$$\begin{array}{ll} ((P \rightarrow Q) \wedge P) \rightarrow Q & \text{Modus Ponens} \\ (P \wedge Q) \rightarrow P \text{ and } (P \wedge Q) \rightarrow Q & \text{Conjunction Elimination} \\ ((P \rightarrow Q) \wedge (Q \rightarrow R)) \rightarrow (P \rightarrow R) & \text{Hypothetical Syllogism} \end{array}$$

Note also that we can derive for any propositions P, Q and S

$$((S \rightarrow P) \wedge (S \rightarrow Q)) \rightarrow (S \rightarrow (P \wedge Q)) \quad (8.3)$$

If we now consider any valid proposition as an object and the existence of a single morphism between propositions P and Q if and only if $P \rightarrow Q$ then we can construct the category of all valid propositions and logical deductions between them, called *Prop*, which we claim is a small

category. From this categorical construction we can see that (8.3) defines a product in $Prop$

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & S & \\
 & \vdots \downarrow h & \\
 P & \longleftarrow P \wedge Q \longrightarrow & Q \\
 & f_P \quad f_Q &
 \end{array}
 \tag{8.4}$$

We can show that the morphism between S and $P \wedge Q$ is unique. Suppose not, then we could have morphisms g, h in $Prop(S, P \wedge Q)$. However, by conjunction elimination $(P \wedge Q) \rightarrow P$ and then by hypothetical syllogism g, h are in $Prop(S, P)$. But, there can only be a single morphism between objects in $Prop$, hence $g = h$. Equalisers also exist in $Prop$ since there can only be a single morphism between any two propositions, consider the following diagram for propositions Z, X, Y :

$$Z \xrightarrow{h} X \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} Y$$

There can only be a single morphism between proposition Z and Y , but $fh, gh \in Prop(Z, Y)$, hence $f = g$. Since $Prop$ has products and equalisers then, by theorem 6.4.2, it is a complete category.

With the above information, we can begin to determine if the functor,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (-)^P &: Prop \rightarrow Prop, \\
 X &\mapsto X^P && \text{(objects),} \\
 (f : X \rightarrow Y) &\mapsto (f^P : X^P \rightarrow Y^P) && \text{(morphisms)}
 \end{aligned}$$

for any fixed proposition P , has a left adjoint. In the above, the notation X^P represents $P \rightarrow X$, that is P implies X . The derivation of this interesting functor will be presented below. But first, showing that this functor preserves limits, consider any product $S \wedge T$ then $(-)^P(S \wedge T) = P \rightarrow (S \wedge T)$ but by conjunction elimination we have $(S \wedge T) \rightarrow S$ and $(S \wedge T) \rightarrow T$ and by hypothetical syllogism we arrive at the following;

$$\begin{aligned}
 (P \rightarrow (S \wedge T)) \wedge ((S \wedge T) \rightarrow S) &\rightarrow (P \rightarrow S) \\
 (P \rightarrow (S \wedge T)) \wedge ((S \wedge T) \rightarrow T) &\rightarrow (P \rightarrow T)
 \end{aligned}$$

From the above we can form the commutative triangle

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & P & \\
 & \swarrow \quad \searrow & \\
 S & \longleftarrow S \wedge T \longrightarrow & T
 \end{array}$$

and considering that P was chosen arbitrarily, then we know this is a product in $Prop$, hence products as conjunctions are preserved. For the required solution set condition we notice that $Z^Y \wedge Y \rightarrow Z$ resembles the evaluation map, which we met in the exponential law for sets example in 8.4.3. Also, as shown in [24], by the deduction theorem,

$$(S \rightarrow (P \rightarrow Q)) \text{ iff } ((S \wedge P) \rightarrow Q)
 \tag{8.5}$$

and by applying modus ponens

$$(S \wedge P) \rightarrow ((P \rightarrow Q) \wedge P)$$

then we have the following triangle, which commutes by hypothetical syllogism

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Q & \longleftarrow & (P \rightarrow Q) \wedge P \\ & \swarrow & \uparrow \\ & & S \wedge P \end{array}$$

Explicitly,

$$\left((S \wedge P) \rightarrow ((P \rightarrow Q) \wedge P) \right) \wedge \left(((P \rightarrow Q) \wedge P) \rightarrow Q \right) \rightarrow \left((S \wedge P) \rightarrow Q \right)$$

Now, similarly to the exponential law example, we can construct the functors $(-\wedge P)$ and $(-)^P$ from $Prop$ to $Prop$ and the triangle becomes

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Q & \xleftarrow{\psi_Q} & (-\wedge P)(-)^P Q & & (-)^P Q \\ & \swarrow a & \uparrow (b\wedge P) & & \uparrow \exists! b \\ & & (-\wedge P)S & & S \end{array} \quad (8.6)$$

Now if we consider the dual diagram of (8.6);

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Q & \longrightarrow & (-^P)(-\wedge P)Q & & (-\wedge P)Q \\ & \searrow b & \downarrow (^P)a & & \downarrow \exists! a \\ & & (-^P)S & & S \end{array} \quad (8.7)$$

Applying hypothetical syllogism, we can confirm the validity of the sequence of propositions in the above diagram. But this becomes clearer when we use the simplified diagram form;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Q & \longrightarrow & (P \rightarrow (Q \wedge P)) \\ & \searrow & \downarrow \\ & & (P \rightarrow S) \end{array}$$

Here, through hypothetical syllogism we see the validity and commutativity of the sequence of propositions. Now if we refer to diagram 8.7 and let $T_i = (-\wedge P)Q_i$ where there exists a single index i for every Q_i in $Prop$, then we have satisfied the solution set condition. Therefore, all of the requirements of Freyd's Adjoint Functor Theorem have been satisfied to prove that $(-\wedge P) \dashv (-)^P$.

Finally, if we state the adjunction in its natural isomorphic form, with the functors applied to any valid propositions S and Q ,

$$\mathbf{Prop}((S \wedge P, Q) \cong \mathbf{Prop}(S, Q^P)$$

then we obtain

$$((S \wedge P) \rightarrow Q) \leftrightarrow (S \rightarrow (P \rightarrow Q))$$

which yields the exportation rule of replacement.

8.5.3 Linear adjunction and subspaces of a normed linear space

Let X be a normed linear space and let $\mathcal{S}(X)$ be the set of all linear subspaces of X . We can form a partially-ordered set $(\mathcal{S}(X), \geq)$ by applying an ordering on the subspaces of X under

containment. That is, for subspaces $U, V \subseteq X$,

$$U \geq V \text{ if and only if } U \supseteq V.$$

In section 2.4.2 it was shown how to construct a category from pre-orders, in a similar fashion, we can construct categories from partial-orders. As a category, then, the objects of $\mathcal{S}(X)$ will correspond to its elements, while the partial ordering relation above will be the unique morphism between two such elements if and only if one contains the other as a subspace. Let Y be another normed linear space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a bounded linear map. Since, for any subspace $X' \subseteq X \in \mathcal{S}(X)$, $\mathcal{S}(f)(X') \subseteq \mathcal{S}(f)(X) \in \mathcal{S}(Y)$ then $\mathcal{S}(f)$ can be represented as the functor $\mathcal{S}(f) : \mathcal{S}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(Y)$. From this point onwards let us use the notation \mathcal{S}_f to reduce the use of parenthesis. Similarly, considering the adjoint operator $f^* : Y^* \rightarrow X^*$, where we know X^* and Y^* are normed linear spaces, we can then represent $\mathcal{S}(f^*)$ as a functor from $\mathcal{S}(Y^*)$ to $\mathcal{S}(X^*)$, where the objects of $\mathcal{S}(Y^*)$ are the spaces of bounded linear functionals on the subspaces of Y and containment between spaces provides ordering. Similarly we will use the notation \mathcal{S}_{f^*} for $\mathcal{S}(f^*)$. Let us pause for a moment here to prove an observation that will be useful below.

Lemma 8.5.1. $\mathcal{S}(X) \cong \mathcal{S}(X^*)$

Proof. Let $i : \mathcal{S}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(X^*)$, $E \mapsto i(E)$ where $i(E)$ is the set of all linear functionals from the normed linear space X to the scalar field \mathbb{K} of X , $g : X \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$, that vanish on E . That is, $g(x) = 0$ for every $x \in E$. We note that i is a contravariant functor with the property that if $E \subset E' \subset X$ then $i(E') \subset i(E) \subset X^*$. Now define the functor $\lambda : \mathcal{S}(X^*) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(X)$, $T^* \mapsto \lambda(T^*)$ such that for every subspace T^* in $\mathcal{S}(X^*)$, $\lambda(T^*)$ is the set of all vectors $v \in X$ where $g(v) = 0$ for every $g : T \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ in T^* . We now show that $\lambda \circ i = 1_{\mathcal{S}(X)}$ and $i \circ \lambda = 1_{\mathcal{S}(X^*)}$. For the former we can see that $E \subseteq \lambda(i(E))$, but let us suppose there exists a $v \in \lambda(i(E))$ that is not in E . Then by the Hahn-Banach Theorem, there exists a $\hat{g} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ where $g(x) = \hat{g}(x) = 0$ for every $x \in E$, then $\hat{g}(v) = g(v) \neq 0$ for $v \notin E$. But, by the definition of λ , $\lambda(i(E))$ is the set of all vectors $v \in X$ where $g(v) = 0$ for every g in $i(E)$. But this is a contradiction and so $v \in E$, then $\lambda(i(E)) = E$, hence $\lambda \circ i = 1_{\mathcal{S}(X)}$. On the other hand, clearly $T^* \subseteq i(\lambda(T^*))$ but let us suppose there exists an $f \in i(\lambda(T^*))$ that is not in T^* . $\lambda(T^*)$ is the set of all vectors $v \in X$ where $g(v) = 0$ for every $g : T \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ in T^* , so if $f \notin T^*$ then $f(v) \neq g(v) = 0$. But $i(\lambda(T^*))$ is the set of all linear functionals $g : X \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ that vanish on $\lambda(T^*)$, then f must also vanish on $\lambda(T^*)$. This is a contradiction, hence $f \in T^*$, $i(\lambda(T^*)) = T^*$, hence $i \circ \lambda = 1_{\mathcal{S}(X^*)}$ and the proof is complete. \square

From this point, the remainder of this application of Freyd's theorem will progress as follows. Firstly, we will show that the functor $F : \mathcal{S}(Y) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(X)$, induced by the inverse of f , is left adjoint to \mathcal{S}_f , but we shall use the morphism only perspective discussed in section 7.3. In applying this method we will naturally derive well-known but important properties of linear algebra. Finally, we will conclude this application by showing that the criterion of Freyd's theorem has been satisfied.

Let us recall section 7.3, the morphism only perspective of adjoint functors. The formulae derived from the natural isomorphisms of 7.3 show an interesting restatement of what it means for F to be a left adjoint. Consider the discussion in that section, but applied to the present functors;

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{S}(X) & \xrightarrow{\mathcal{S}_f} & \mathcal{S}(Y) \\ \downarrow i & & \downarrow j \\ \mathcal{S}(X^*) & \xleftarrow{\mathcal{S}_{f^*}} & \mathcal{S}(Y^*) \end{array} \quad (8.8)$$

Here, the morphism j corresponds to the isomorphism i in lemma 8.5.1, for normed linear space Y . First, for any subspace $D \in \mathcal{S}(Y)$ and $C \in \mathcal{S}(X)$;

$$F \dashv \mathcal{S}_f \text{ means equivalently } D \geq \mathcal{S}_f(C) \\ \text{if and only if } F(D) \geq C$$

This definition suggests that for each object E in $\mathcal{S}(Y)$, $F(E)$ corresponds to $f^{-1}(E)$. Let us also note that if E is an object of $\mathcal{S}(Y)$, then $j(E)$ is the subspace of functionals that vanish on E . $\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(j(E))$ is then the space of functionals on X obtained by the composition of elements of $j(E)$ with f , that is, if $g \in j(E)$ then $f^*(g) = g \circ f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$, where $g|_E = 0$. Finally, $i^{-1}(\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(j(E)))$ is the subspace of vectors $v \in X$ such that $g(f(v)) = 0$ for all g in $j(E)$. That is, $i^{-1}(\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(j(E))) = F(E) = f^{-1}(E)$ seems to follow plausibly. In particular, if $E = \{0\}$, then $j(E)$ is the space of functionals which vanish on $\{0\}$, which is of course all of Y^* . Now $\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(Y^*)$ is the subspace of X^* corresponding to the image of f^* , from which we obtain the well-known fact that

$$Im(f^*) = Ker(f)^\perp$$

in any inner-product space, or when expressed functorially

$$i(F(\{0\})) = \mathcal{S}_{f^*}(Y^*)$$

which is saying that the subspace of functionals on X which vanish on the subspace $F(\{0\})$ ($= Ker(f)$) consists exclusively of functionals of the form $f^*(g)$, where g is a functional on Y . Conversely, if E is an object of $\mathcal{S}(X)$, then $j(\mathcal{S}_f(E))$ is the subspace of functionals on Y which vanish on $f(E)$. In particular, if $E = X$, then $j(\mathcal{S}_f(X))$ consists of functionals which vanish on $Im(f)$, so $f^*(g) = g \circ f = 0$. Here we are reminded of the identity

$$Ker(f^*) = \overline{Im(f)}^\perp$$

in Hilbert space.

Showing carefully that $\mathcal{S}_{f^*} \circ j = i \circ F$ is not altogether trivial. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(j(E))$ is a subspace of $i(F(E))$, but the interesting part is to show that any functional h in $i(F(E))$ is of the form $g \circ f$ for some functional g belonging to $j(E)$. So, if $K(h)$ denotes the kernel of h , that is $K(h) = \{x \in X | h(x) = 0\}$, then we know that $K(h) \geq F(E)$, that is $F(E)$ must be contained in $K(h)$. Let $v \in X \setminus K(h)$, then since $Ker(f)$ is naturally contained in $F(E)$, we can be sure that neither $h(v)$ nor $f(v)$ is zero. Now, $X = span\{K(h), v\}$, while $f(v)$ and $\mathcal{S}_f(K(h))$ span a subspace of Y corresponding to $\mathcal{S}_f(X)$. Let us define a functional $g_1 : \mathcal{S}_f(X) \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$, where the domain is a linear subspace of Y , such that $g_1(f(v)) = h(v)$, and $g_1|_{\mathcal{S}_f(K(h))} = 0$. Under this definition, note that for any vector u in X , we can write $u = k + sv$, where k belongs to $K(h)$, and s is a scalar, hence $h(u) = h(k + sv) = s.h(v) = s.g_1(f(v)) = g_1(f(sv)) = g_1(f(k) + f(sv)) = g_1(f(u))$. So $g_1 \circ f$ agrees with the definition of h on X , although g_1 itself is only defined on $\mathcal{S}_f(X)$. To complete the argument we need an extension of g_1 to all of Y . The existence of such an extension, $g : Y \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$, is provided to us for bounded linear functionals on normed linear spaces X and Y through the Hahn-Banach Theorem.

Freyd's theorem comes into play implicitly in this example. That is, if we consider the criteria of limit preservation, \mathcal{S}_f must preserve limits, for if it did not then we may have encountered the situation where an unbounded linear functional in Y^* is mapped to a bounded, or unbounded, linear functional in X^* . To elaborate on this, consider the limit of $\mathcal{S}(X)$, similarly for $\mathcal{S}(Y)$. If we consider any partially ordered set within $\mathcal{S}(X)$ as a diagram, then a cone will be an object of $\mathcal{S}(X)$, a subspace of X , which contains the diagram. If we take the intersection of all cones over the diagram, then we arrive at the limit, which represents the least upper bound or the supremum. When we transport the cones, limit and diagram into $\mathcal{S}(Y)$ then any function

$h : E \rightarrow E'$ in $\mathcal{S}(X)$ becomes $\mathcal{S}_f(h) : \mathcal{S}_f(E) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_f(E')$ in $\mathcal{S}(Y)$, preserving the ordering under containment. Now, referring to diagram 8.8, let L be a limit in $\mathcal{S}(X)$, then $\mathcal{S}_f(L)$ is a limit, the supremum, in $\mathcal{S}(Y)$. Since j is a contravariant functor it will reverse the partial ordering and so $j(\mathcal{S}_f(L))$ in $\mathcal{S}(Y^*)$ will be an infimum. Now for our adjoint operator f^* , or any adjoint operator, if $g = j(\mathcal{S}_f(L)) : Y \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ is bounded then $f^*(g) : X \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ is bounded. And since \mathcal{S}_{f^*} is induced by f^* , we can see that $\mathcal{S}_{f^*}(j(\mathcal{S}_f(L)))$ is a subspace of bounded linear functionals. If \mathcal{S}_f did not preserve limits, then $g = j(\mathcal{S}_f(L))$ may have been unbounded and hence, \mathcal{S}_{f^*} would not be mapping bounded linear functionals of Y to bounded linear functionals of X , as we have assumed for most of the discussion in this example.

In our present context, the solution set condition says that for any subspace E of Y there is a unique subspace S_E of X such that for any subspace H of X for which E contains $\mathcal{S}_f(H)$, it follows that S_E contains H and E contains $\mathcal{S}_f(S_E)$ contains $\mathcal{S}_f(H)$. The maximal subspace of E which is also in the image of \mathcal{S}_f is naturally the intersection A of E with $\mathcal{S}_f(X)$. If we then define $S_E = F(A)$, then $A = \mathcal{S}_f(F(A))$ must contain $\mathcal{S}_f(H)$ if this latter is contained in E , and at the same time H must be contained in $F(A)$. Although we haven't specifically relied on this property as such in order to construct F , we have implicitly relied on the equivalent fact that for any subspace E of Y , $f^{-1}(E)$ is the maximal subspace S of X for which $f(S)$ is contained in E .

8.5.4 Topological spaces

In this example we consider the functors F and G and knowing $F \dashv G$ we apply Freyd's theorem to understand and determine what limits are being preserved. Let us begin by defining the functors as follows;

$$F : \mathbf{Set} \rightarrow \mathbf{Top}$$

$$X \mapsto (X, \mathcal{P}(X))$$

$$(f : X \rightarrow Y) \mapsto (Ff : (X, \mathcal{P}(X)) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{P}(Y)))$$

$$G : \mathbf{Top} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$$

$$(X, \mathcal{T}) \mapsto X$$

$$(g : (X, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{T})) \mapsto (Gg : X \rightarrow Y)$$

where (X, \mathcal{T}) is the topology \mathcal{T} over set X and $\mathcal{P}(X)$ is the powerset of X . Here F sends sets and functions to their discrete topologies and continuous functions, where the discrete topology of a set is the powerset of that set and each subset is open. Furthermore, G sends a topology to its underlying set and continuous morphisms to functions. What are the limits in the domain of G that Freyd's theorem states must be preserved? To answer this, consider a diagram to be topological spaces with continuous functions between, then a cone over the diagram will be a topological space with continuous functions to all of the topological spaces forming the diagram. One such cone is the box topology, which can be constructed by taking the Cartesian product of the underlying sets of each topological space, X_i , and the products of the open subsets of each topology, that is, the topological space,

$$\left(\prod_{i \in I} X_i, \mathcal{T} \right),$$

where \mathcal{T} is generated by the basis,

$$\left\{ \prod_{i \in I} U_i \mid U_i \text{ open in } X_i \right\}$$

In the case of the product of infinite topological spaces, the product topology, defined similarly to the box topology except in that $U_i = X_i$ for all but finitely many $i \in I$, is the coarsest topology in which the projections are continuous and hence this forms a limit in **Top**. In the finite case, the product topology is still the coarsest topology and hence a limit, but in this case it is equivalent to the box topology. Regarding the limit's preservation, it's clear that when the topological structure and continuity are forgotten in **Set**, all that will remain are the underlying sets and functions forming a cartesian product, a limit in **Set**.

Bibliography

- [1] America, P., Rutten, Jan. (1989). Solving reflexive domain equations in a category of complete metric spaces. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*, 39. 343-375.
- [2] Arbib M. A., Manes E. G. (1975). *Arrows, structures, and functors : the categorical imperative*. New York. Academic Press.
- [3] Awodey S. (2010). *Category theory (2nd ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
- [4] Baggett L. W. (1991). *Functional analysis* Retrieved from website: <http://spot.colorado.edu/~baggett/functional.html>
- [5] Borceux F. (1994). *Handbook of categorical algebra 1: Basic category theory*. Cambridge. UK. Cambridge University Press.
- [6] Brittenham M. (n.d.). *Free Groups*. Retrieved from the University of Nebraska at Lincoln website: <https://www.math.unl.edu/~mbrittenham2/classwk/990s08/public/myasnikov.1.free.groups.pdf>
- [7] Bunge, M. (2018). *Introduction. A Personal Tribute to Peter Freyd and Bill Lawvere*. Tbilisi Mathematical Journal. 10. i-x. 10.1515/tmj-2017-0114.
- [8] Fraleigh J. B. (1994). *A first course in abstract algebra (5th ed.)*. Massachusetts. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
- [9] Kreyszig E. (1978). *Introductory functional analysis with applications*. New York. John Wiley & Sons.
- [10] Lang S. (2002). *Algebra (3rd ed.)*. New York. Springer-Verlag.
- [11] Lawvere F. W. (2006). Adjointness in foundations. *Reprints in theory and applications of categories, No. 16*. 1-16.
- [12] Leinster T. (2014). *Basic Category Theory*. Cambridge. UK. Cambridge University Press.
- [13] Mac Lane S. (1970). The Influence of M. H. Stone on the origins of category theory. *Functional analysis and related fields*. 228-241. Heidelberg, Berlin, Germany. Springer.
- [14] Mac Lane S. (1971). Categorical algebra and set-theoretic foundations. Axiomatic set theory. *Proceedings of symposia in pure mathematics, 13 part 1*. 231-240.
- [15] Mac Lane S. (1998). *Categories for the Working Mathematician (2nd ed.)*. New York. Springer-Science+Business Media.
- [16] nLab authors. (2018). *Limits and colimits by example*. Retrieved from website: <https://ncatlab.org/nlab/show/limits+and+colimits+by+example>
- [17] Palmquist P.H. (1974). Adjoint functors induced by adjoint linear transformations. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 44, No. 2, 251-254.

- [18] Renzo C. (n.d.). *Introduction to topology*. Retrieved from the Colorado State University website: <http://www.math.colostate.edu/~renzo/teaching/Topology10/Notes.pdf>
- [19] Rosen K. H. (2007). *Discrete mathematics and its applications. (6th ed.)*. New York. McGraw-Hill.
- [20] Rotman J. J. (2008). *An introduction to homological algebra. (2nd ed.)*. New York. Springer.
- [21] Schmitt W. R. (n.d.). *A concrete introduction to categories*. Retrieved from the George Washington University website: <http://home.gwu.edu/~wschmitt/papers/cat.pdf>
- [22] Schubert H. (1972). *Categories*. Berlin. Springer-Verlag.
- [23] Shulman M. A. (2008). *Set theory for category theory*. arXiv:0810.1279v2 [math.CT].
- [24] Smith K. (2008). *Adjoint functors in algebra, topology and mathematical logic*. Retrieved from the University of Capetown website: <https://people.cs.uct.ac.za/~ksmith/adjoint.pdf>
- [25] Spivak D. I. (2013). *Category theory for scientists*. Retrieved from online textbook website: <http://math.mit.edu/~dspivak/teaching/sp13/CT4S-static.pdf>
- [26] Spivak D. I. (2014). *Category for the sciences*. Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England. The MIT Press.
- [27] Terry C. (n.d.). *What the functor?: Category theory and the concept of adjointness*. Retrieved from the University of Chicago website: <http://math.uchicago.edu/~may/VIGRE/VIGRE2008/REUPapers/Terry.pdf>